

COMMUNICATION OVER THE CITY OF STARS

INSPECTING QUEZON
CITY'S EVOLUTION AS
A DISCOURSE HUB

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COMMUNICATION OVER THE CITY OF STARS: INSPECTING QUEZON CITY'S EVOLUTION AS A DISCOURSE HUB

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Abstract

Quezon City is an important place in the Philippines not only in terms of its history, but also with its ties to the different branches of government and mainstream media. As a former capital of the Philippines and being the home to big network stations that broadcast all over the country, the city can be said to be integral to the development of communication in the country. Furthermore, this paper will assess the status of communication in a younger demographic to look at how do they make use of communication devices in their lives and deal with the changes of the mediums used and how does it affect the cultural aspect of the city.

Keywords: *communication, development, Quezon City*

Introduction

Since its foundation on October 12, 1939, Quezon City (QC) has become one of the important cities of the area that would become the National Capital Region (NCR). As of today, the city is the largest city in Luzon and the most populous city in the Philippines. Founded to seat in the different government branches in an area that cannot be raided by the bay area, the city is brought from eight estates and the towns located in the cities of Caloocan, San Juan, Marikina, Pasig, and the province of Rizal, particularly in the towns located in Rodrigue and San Mateo. Almost synonymous to the city are the different branches of government, business, education, broadcast communication, and entertainment found within the central parts of the city, particularly in the Diliman Quadrangle, Araneta City, and Eastwood City.

It is formerly the capital of the city, which was declared on October 12, 1949, which was also its 10th Founding Anniversary, before being reverted again for Manila become the capital. As the base for many communication networks along with its heavy ties to the formation the Philippine government, the influence of this city towards the evolution of communication is essential to recognize, as it is integral for what the city is recognized for. The purpose of this paper is to not only tell the significance of the city as a center of communication, but to also reflect on it as well as how did it evolve during the years, and how well did it improve along with the city's growth.

While it will be not possible to turn back time and investigate all areas located within the city where it became integral part of our national interaction as well as international relations, there will be factual pieces that will be utilized in this paper that will be used to piece out the development of the city as an effective center for communication. This paper will also heavily utilize web pages that can be used to list down the different communication mediums, in the form of radio and television, that are especially influential here in the city.

Brief History of the City

According to the official government website of the city, its origins begin on September 28, 1939, when the National Assembly approved Bill No. 1206 as Commonwealth Act No. 502, otherwise known as the Charter of Quezon City. Signed by President Manuel Luis Quezon on October 12, 1939, the law defined the boundaries of the city and gave it an area of 7,000 hectares carved out of the towns of Caloocan, San Juan, Marikina, Pasig, and Mandaluyong, which is all part of Rizal Province. Since its creation, there are four revisions to how the city's boundaries are defined. Originally, it only had only about 7,000 hectares extending from La Loma to Marikina River and from Pasong Tamo River down to Wack Wack Golf Club in Mandaluyong. During the height of the Second World War, the city also saw battles in the areas of Novaliches, Talipapa, and the University area of the University of the Philippines in Diliman. The city is also turned into a chartered city, called the City of Greater Manila or Greater Manila Area. After the war, then President Sergio Osmeña signed Executive Order No. 58, also known as the Reducing the Territory of the City of Greater Manila which would then turn the areas back into their respective statuses before the war.

President Manuel L. Quezon and Don Alejandro Rocés Sr., having breakfast at the Malacañang, where Rocés pitched out a plan for a new capital city just outside of the city of Manila. (Source: Don Alejandro Rocés Sr. Facebook Page)

The final amendment was made on June 16, 1956, by virtue of RA 1575 with the City's area, of 15,106 hectares. This is the present official territorial boundary of Quezon City. However, graphical plots made on this present boundary of the city gave an area of 16,112 hectares, about a thousand hectares more than its officially declared land area. The original physical plan of the city was prepared in 1940 by Harry T. Frost, an architectural adviser of the Commonwealth. He reflected a big quadrangle in the heart of the City from which four (4) avenues radiated toward the outskirts with rotundas placed on the four (4) corners, the largest being a 26-hectare elliptical center, known as the Quezon City Memorial Circle (abbreviated as QCMC).

The original plans for the new capital city. (Source: Rappler)

By the virtue of the Republic Act No. 333 on July 17, 1948, the city was made to be the capital of the Philippines. The Act created the Capital City Planning Commission which was tasked to prepare the general development plan and supervise the improvements to be done in the Capital City. It was formally introduced as the national capital of the Philippines on October 12, 1949, with President Elpidio Quirino laying the cornerstone of the proposed Capitol Building at Constitution Hills. (now called Barangay New Era, inspired by the Iglesia ni Cristo sect). The Welcome Arch (now Mabuhay Rotunda) at the boundary of Manila and Quezon City was built, defining the coverage of the city to be 156.60 square kilometers or 60 square miles. For 27 years, Quezon City held the distinct status of being the nation's capital. In the year 1975, the city became part of the larger urban governance scheme that is Metro Manila, with the creation of the Metropolitan Manila Commission by virtue of Presidential Decree 824. On July 24, 1976, then President Ferdinand E. Marcos issued Presidential Decree No. 940, conferring the role of the nation's capital to Metro Manila, hence the name National Capital Region (abbreviated as NCR).

The Welcome Rotonda marker, shown in the 1965 issue of the Meralco Magazine, and the Rotonda as it is now today, viewed from above (Source: History of Barangays and Communities in Quezon City Facebook Page)

While it is no longer the nation's capital city, it has proved to be a vast and teeming city with a steadily increasing income and occupation of one-third of Metro Manila's total land area. It now serves as the Philippines' government center with the legislature and other important government offices located in the area. President Manuel Quezon himself served as the city's first Mayor and he later appointed Tomas Morato to the position. A long line of distinguished Mayors succeeded Morato in the stewardship of the city as follows: Ponciano Bernardo, Nicanor Roxas, Ignacio Santos Diaz, Norberto Amoranto, Adelina Rodriguez, Brigido Simon, Jr., Ishmael Mathay, Jr., Feliciano Belmonte, Jr., Herbert Constantine Bautista, and the incumbent Ma. Josefina Tanya Belmonte.

The eleven mayors of Quezon City, not including the mayors of the City of Greater Manila during the Second World War. Also shown in the picture is the flag of the city. (Source: Quezon City Government and Quezon City Public Library (QCPL Facebook Page))

Albeit called a young city, there have been events that shaped the nation's course of history that took place in the city's territory. This is evident with the National Centennial Commission, tasked to spearhead appropriate remembrance of 100 years of Philippine Independence, which has included Quezon City in the "Freedom Trail" highlighting places and important events in the struggle for freedom and sovereignty, including the historic "Cry of Pugad Lawin" led by revolutionary hero Andres Bonifacio on August 23, 1896, and the People Power Revolution in EDSA that toppled the regime of dictator Ferdinand E. Marcos Sr. and the installation of Corazon C. Aquino, as the 11th President of the Philippines. The city is also the first local government to adapt and have a computerized real estate appraisal and payment system. In 2015, the local government of the city also developed a database system for real

estate that includes around 400,000 property units with the capacity to record payments. Currently, QC stands with six political districts, under the virtue of Republic Act No. 10170, which was approved on July 02, 2012, by former president Benigno “Noynoy” Aquino III.

The six congressional districts (left), which is also subdivided into the 142 barangays (right) of Quezon City. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Divisions of the City

As a planned city, it is easier to identify the different parts of the city and what it is called, although there are already existing districts in the area before it was established, which are the districts of San Francisco del Monte, Novaliches, and Cubao. Eventually, there are other districts that are formed in the city, mostly named after plants, such as the areas of Diliman, Mangga, Kamuning, Kamias, and Masambong, or the commonalities that are found within there, like Balingasa and Balintawak. Another motif that can be found within the districts are names of saints, such as San Isidro Galas, San Martin de Porres, Socorro, San Antonio, and San Isidro Labrador. There are also places that came from words or phrases, as well as people. This is reflected in the names of Pinagkaisahan, Marilag, Villa Maria Clara, Horseshoe, Nagkaisang Nayon, and Fairview. This paper would not ponder on the history of the already existing districts of the city, but it is imperative that the origins of how these places are known. Shown in the table below are the origins of the names per barangay in the city, which are listed alphabetically.

Barangay Name	Origin
Alicia	Alicia Quirino
Amihan	Northeast Monsoon
Apolonio Samson	Barrio Kangkong / Apolonio Samson
Aurora	Aurora Quezon
Baesa	Babaeng Nag-iisa (Lone Woman)

Bagbag	Bagbag (Broken Up Soil)
Bagong Lipunan Ng Crame	Camp General Rafael T. Crame (Camp Crame)
Bagong Pag-asa	Ramon Magsaysay's Speech
Bagong Silangan	Bagong Silangan (East Triangle Relocation)
Bagumbayan	Bagong Bayan (New Village)
Bagumbuhay	Bagong Buhay (New Life)
Bahay Toro	Cattle Farm
Balingasa	Balun ng Gasang (Artesian Wells)
Balong Bato	Balun ng Bato (Stone Wells)
Batasan Hills	Batasang Pambansa Complex
Bayanihan	Bayanihan (Community Spirit) / Bayanihan Social Club
Blue Ridge A	Blue Ridge Subdivision
Blue Ridge B	Blue Ridge Subdivision
Botocan	Botocan Transmission Line
Bungad	Front of San Francisco del Monte (Frisco)
Camp Aguinaldo	Camp General Emilio Aguinaldo (CGEA)
Capri	Goat
Central	Central Part of Quezon City
Claro	Clarity
Commonwealth	Commonwealth Avenue
Culiat	Cuiat (Coarse Woody Vines)
Damar	Dona Margarita Soriano
Damayan	Damayan (Sympathize)
Damayang Lagi	Damayang Lagi (Always Empathetic)
Del Monte	Del Monte Avenue / San Francisco del Monte
Dioquino Zobel	Dioquino Zobel
Doña Imelda	Doña Imelda
Doña Josefa	Doña Josefa
Don Manuel	Don Manuel
Duyan-Duyan	Duyan (Hammock)
East Kamias	Kamias (<i>Averrhoa bilimbi</i>)
E. Rodriguez	Eulogio Rodriguez Sr.
Escopa I	ISCOPA / 1st Company of the Philippine Army
Escopa II	ISCOPA / 1st Company of the Philippine Army
Escopa III	ISCOPA / 1st Company of the Philippine Army
Escopa IV	ISCOPA / 1st Company of the Philippine Army
Fairview	Fairview

Greater Lagro	Lagro Subdivision
Gulod	Gulod (Hilltop)
Holy Spirit	Holy Spirit Parish
Horseshoe	Horseshoe Village
Immaculate Concepcion	Immaculate Conception / Cubao Cathedral
Kaligayahan	Barrio Binugsok / Kaligayahan (Cheerfulness)
Kalusugan	Health / St. Lukes Medical Center
Kamuning	Kamuning (<i>Murraya paniculata</i>)
Katipunan	Kataastaasan, Kagalangalangang Katipunan ng mga Anak ng Bayan (KKK)
Kaunlaran	Kaunlaran (Prosperity)
Kristong Hari	Christ the King
Krus Na Ligas	Ligas (<i>Semecarpus cuneiformis</i>)
Laging Handa	Laging Handa (Always Prepared) / Boy Scouts of the Philippines
Libis	Hillside / Libis River
Lourdes	Our Lady of Lourdes
Loyola Heights	St. Ignatius of Loyola
Maharlika	Maharlika (Royalty)
Malaya	Malaya (Free)
Mangga	Mangga (<i>Mangifera indica</i>)
Manresa	Manresa, Spain
Mariana	Mariana Wilson
Mariblo	Maria Diablo / Mariblo Creek
Marilag	Marilag (Beautiful)
Masagana	Masagana (Bountiful)
Masambong	Sambong (<i>Blumea balsamifera</i>)
Matandang Balara	Balara (Drum)
Milagrosa	Our Lady of the Miraculous Medal
Nagkaisang Nayon	Nagkaisang Nayon (United Village)
Nayong Kanluran	Nayong Kaunlaran (Village of Progress)
New Era (Constitution Hills)	Iglesia ni Cristo
North Fairview	Fairview
Novaliches Proper (Bayan)	Novaliches, Spain / Manuel Pavia y Lacy
N. S. Amoranto (Gintong Silahis)	Norberto Amoranto
Obrero	Worker / Worker's Community
Old Capitol Site	Old City Hall Site of Quezon City
Paang Bundok	Paang Bundok (Foot of the Mountain)

Pag-ibig Sa Nayon	Pag-ibig sa Nayon (Love in the Village)
Paligsahan	Paligsahan (Competition)
Paltok	Paltok (Highland)
Pansol	Sitio Pansol / Balara (Drum)
Paraiso	Paradise
Pasong Putik Proper (Pasong Putik)	Muddy Area
Pasong Tamo	Tamo (<i>Begonia tamo</i>)
Payatas	Payat sa Taas (Thin at the Top)
Phil-Am	Philippine American Life Insurance Company / AIA Philippines
Pinagkaisahan	Pagkakaisa (Unity)
Pinyahan	Pineapple / Pineapple Cultivation
Project 6	People's Homesite and Housing Corporation (PHHC)
Quirino 2-A	Elpidio Quirino
Quirino 2-B	Elpidio Quirino
Quirino 2-C	Elpidio Quirino
Quirino 3-A	Elpidio Quirino
Ramon Magsaysay	Ramon Magsaysay
Roxas	People's Homesite and Housing Corporation (PHHC) / Manuel Roxas
Sacred Heart	Sacred Heart Parish
Saint Ignatius	St. Ignatius of Loyola
Saint Peter	St. Peter
Salvacion	Salvation
San Agustin	St. Augustine of Hippo
San Antonio	Barrio Bodega / St. Anthony of Padua
San Bartolome	St. Bartholomew
Sangandaan	Sanga-Sangang Daan (Cross Roads)
San Isidro	Galas / St. Isidore the Laborer
San Isidro Labrador	Barrio Malamig / St. Isidore the Laborer
San Jose	Barrio La Loma / St. Joseph
San Martin De Porres	St. Martin of Porres
San Roque	St. Roch
Santa Cruz	Holy Cross
Santa Lucia	St. Lucy
Santa Monica	St. Monica
Santa Teresita	St. Therese of the Child Jesus
Santo Cristo	Holy Cross

Santo Domingo (Matalahib)	Talahib (<i>Saccharum spontaneum</i>) / St. Dominic
Santol	Santol (<i>Sandoricum koetjape</i>)
Santo Niño	Child Jesus
San Vicente	St. Vincent Ferrer
Sauyo	Original Name
Siena	Siena College of Quezon City
Sikatuna Village	Datu Sikatuna
Silangan	East Portion of Cubao
Socorro	Our Lady of Prompt Succor
South Triangle	Triangle Park
Tagumpay	Tagumpay (Victory)
Talayan	Talayan Creek / Part of Caloocan
Talipapa	Fish Market / Part of Caloocan
Tandang Sora	Barrio Banlat / Melchora Aquino
Tatalon	Barrio Tatalon / Tatalon Estate
Teachers Village East	National Housing Authority (NHA)
Teachers Village West	National Housing Authority (NHA)
Ugong Norte	Ogong / Part of Rizal
Unang Sigaw	Cry of Pugadlawin
U.P. Campus	University of the Philippines
U.P. Village	University of the Philippines
Valencia	Valencia, Spain
Vasra	VASRA / Visayas Avenue Subdivision Residents' Association
Veterans Village	People's Homesite and Housing Corporation (PHHC) / Veterans Area
Villa Maria Clara	Maria Clara de los Santos (Rizal Novel Character)
West Kamias	Kamias (<i>Averrhoa bilimbi</i>)
West Triangle	Triangle Park
White Plains	White Plains, New York

To properly distinguish these places, the national government had assigned six districts that divide the city areas into six regions, which are subdivided by 142 barangays, which are then the old barrios and the brought-up land from the different estates. While there are still private estates in the city, these places are now a part of a respective barangay in the city. The table below are the different divisions of the city per congressional district and the barangays that are associated within it.

Congressional District 1	Alicia, Bagong Pag-asa, Bahay Toro, Balingasa, Bungad, Damar, Damayan, Del Monte, Katipunan, Mariblo, Masambong, N.S. Amoranto (Gintong Silahis), Nayong Kanluran, Paang Bundok, Pag-ibig sa Nayon,
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	Paltok, Paraiso, Phil-Am, Ramon Magsaysay, Salvacion, San Antonio, San Isidro Labrador, San Jose, Santa Cruz, Santa Teresita, Santo Cristo, Talayan, Vasra, Veterans Village and West Triangle
Congressional District 2	Bagong Silangan, Batasan Hills, Commonwealth, Holy Spirit and Payatas
Congressional District 3	Amihan, Bagumbuhay, Bagumbayan, Bayanihan, Blue Ridge A, Blue Ridge B, Camp Aguinaldo, Claro, Dioquino Zobel, Duyan-Duyan, E. Rodriguez, East Kamias, Escopa I, Escopa II, Escopa III, Escopa IV, Libis, Loyola Heights, Mangga, Marilag, Masagana, Matandang Balara, Milagrosa, Pansol, Quirino 2-A, Quirino 2-B, Quirino 2-C, Quirino 3-A, Saint Ignatius, San Roque, Silangan, Socorro, Tagumpay, Ugong Norte, Villa Maria Clara, West Kamias and White Plains
Congressional District 4	Bagong Lipunan ng Crame, Botocan, Central, Kristong Hari, Damayang Lagi, Doña Aurora, Doña Imelda, Doña Josefa, Don Manuel, East Triangle, Horseshoe, Immaculate Conception, Kalusugan, Kamuning, Kaunlaran, Krus na Ligas, Laging Handa, Malaya, Mariana, Obrero, Old Capitol Site, Paligsahan, Pinyahan, Pinagkaisahan, Roxas, Sacred Heart, San Isidro Galas, San Martin de Porres, San Vicente, Santo Niño, Santol, Sikatuna Village, South Triangle, Tatalon, Teachers Village East, Teachers Village West, U.P. Campus, U.P. Village and Valencia
Congressional District 5	Bagbag, Capri, Fairview, Greater Lagro, Gulod, Kaligayahan, Nagkaisang Nayon, North Fairview, Novaliches Proper, Pasong Putik Proper, San Agustin, San Bartolome, Santa Lucia and Santa Monica
Congressional District 6	Apolonio Samson, Baesa, Balon-Bato, Culiati, New Era, Pasong Tamo, Sangandaan, Sauyo, Talipapa, Tandang Sora and Unang Sigaw

The City as a Discourse Hub

What distinguishes the city from other cities in the National Capital Region is its importance in the establishment of communication in the country, which is evident with the big news stations that are being stationed here and broadcasting in the city. In this section, we will look at each of them and examine how are they doing now and what they have done not only in the history of the Philippines, but also their impact while they are on air. To properly observe these places, the areas will be divided into their respective congressional districts and how many of places are there that use communication on a regular basis. It is a guarantee that it will not cover all of them, as the city is big, but this paper will focus on the more important ones.

According to the Quezon City's official website, there are eleven local television networks, six cable television stations, seven AM radio stations, and four FM radio stations. These are only the ones that are registered to them as an official running station with a given frequency and programming, but there are also online radio stations and channels that are running on other platforms, particularly on the social media and sharing site, Facebook. Radio Garden, a website where one can stream radio stations in other country, lists that there are ten available radio stations in the city. The government of the city also reports in their website that the number of MERALCO customers was pegged at 512,225 of which 461,645 of the metered connections or 90.1% were residential, 49,082 or 9.6% commercial, 1,110 or 0.2% industrial and 418 were for streetlights. The liberalization of the telecommunication industry, which was

noted by the local government, allowed for five telephone companies to be present in the area, as well as cellular mobile companies and broadband services. As of today, these companies have expanded and attracted more customers and users, which is particularly evident with the boom of mobile wallet applications that support the loading system of cellular mobile phones as well as providing mobile data.

A photo of the Quezon Memorial Circle taken from the opening of East Avenue. Also seen in the photo is the communication tower of People's Television Network (PTV), which can be viewed on free television on Channel 4. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

The transmitter tower of Global Media Arts (GMA) in Culiat, Quezon City which is named as the Tower of Power (Source: Infinitri Creatives)

Screenshots from the “Buy Load” option of the mobile wallet application, GCash. GCash provides a reliable one-stop shop from buying load, mobile data, bills, savings, and donations. This availability for all makes GCash an application that is common to the citizens of the city. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Starting off with Congressional District 1 of the city, which is commonly known for the introduction of the first SM Supermall in the country, which is SM North EDSA. The introduction of a shopping mall in this part of the city led to major developments in the community that are living there, along with the introduction of different businesses, hospitals, entertainment centers, schools, and media stations. But before the introduction of SM North, the place has also been inhabited in the areas of the old Barrio Tatalon, which is now distributed into two districts, the other being Congressional District 4. Other places in the district are also famous, such as La Loma and Sto. Domingo, famous for their stalls of roasted pig or lechon and the Sto. Domingo Church, respectively.

Radio stations are common in this district, with the stations of REPubl1KA FM1 87.5 FM, Capital FM2 104.3 FM, Crossover 105.1 FM, Q Radio 105.1 FM, Wish 107.5 FM, Radyo Pilipinas AM 738, Radyo Veritas AM 846, Radyo Veritas Asia, Radyo Pilipinas AM 918, Dominican Students' Media Center Philippines, Nomixx Online Radio, AESTHETIC MOA FM, Inquirer Radyo 990 AM, Now Radio AM 1098, ACI News Radio AM 1170, ACI News Radio AM 1206, and ACI News Radio AM 1278.

A common scenery at SM North EDSA, where crowds are entering and exiting the mall in this crossing. Just in front of the mall are the jeepney terminals where people can go to their homes or to other places after shopping inside. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

The television stations in this area are those that can be funded by the national government, which include CNN Philippines under Radio Philippines Network (RPN) and the People's Television Network (PTV), which also has a Muslim television channel named Salaam TV. UNTV also was housed in EDSA, before being relocated to Bagong Barrio West in Caloocan, but a UNTV Broadcast Tower will be built soon in the district. Communication devices can be found in the district, especially in places like malls and stalls, which are common in the businesses located in Banawe Street and the malls in North EDSA – particularly SM North EDSA, SM North EDSA Annex, Trinoma Mall, and Vertis North. There is also the old building of IBC 13, which then moved now to Zuzuaregui.

Radio stations in Quezon City via Radio Garden. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Photos of the UNTV Millennium Tower, currently being built at North EDSA. This will serve as the communications tower of the UNTV and its radio channels that are under the company. (Source: Emerging Philippines)

There are no notable communication hubs in Congressional District 2 except for a handful of business process outsourcing (BPO) companies that can be found along Commonwealth Avenue and two malls that are adjacent to each other, which are Ever Gotesco Commonwealth and Shopwise Commonwealth, with the exception of Puyat Broadcasting Corporation (PBC) in One Felicity Center that is adjacent to Shopwise Commonwealth. This is because this is the district where the National Government Complex (NGC) II can be found. This means that the Batasang Pambansa Complex, the Commission of Audit for the National Capital Region and Region IV-A (Calabarzon), the Sandiganbayan, the Department of Social Welfare and Development, and a future building for the Public Attorney's Office (PAO), can be found. Being closer to government buildings, communication is very much active here, especially when media and people will flock to the place when there's a State of the Nation Address given by the President of the Philippines. This district is also the place of Batasan Hills National High School, the most populous high school in the country, which is also in front of the President Corazon Aquino Elementary School and adjacent with the branch of Quezon City University, the local university of the city.

UNTV

NEWS & RESCUE

UNTV's Logo as of April 04, 2019. (Source: UNTV News & Rescue Facebook Page)

Façade of the Commission of Audit (COA) main building, located in Batasan Hills and is near the Sandiganbayan and the Batasang Pambansa Complex. The regional office for Region IV-A or Calabarzon is located here. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Congressional District 3 is also abundant with interesting places for media and entertainment, although most of them are now defunct and now demolished to give way for industrialization in the area. The most important of these now obsolete media places is the Broadcast City, a place where the headquarters of three broadcasting networks can be found, namely the Banahaw Broadcasting Corporation (BBC), Radio Philippines Network (RPN), and the Intercontinental Broadcasting Corporation (IBC). The Broadcast City was then made defunct after the takeover of the new transition government that seized the area and gave the frequencies back to the owners that were taken away their broadcasting rights to the public. After that, the Broadcast City was left in shambles and was instead replaced by a commercial condominium called the Larossa Condominium. Out of all the stations in Broadcast City, only IBC is only the one standing, which is in near Zuzuareggi and Capitol Hills Drive in Matandang (Old) Balara. Other radio stations that can be found in the district is FYA Radio, V81 Radio and DWDD AFP Radio 1134 AM. One television channel can be found in the district, which is Living Asia Channel.

The Filipino Educational Channel

IBC 13's Cover Photo on March 22, 2022. (Source: IBC 13 Facebook Page)

Mid-rise condominiums in Primehomes Capitol Hills, where the old Broadcast City is situated. (Source: Laselva in Capitol Hills Condominium)

The most active district in terms of bringing communication to the public is Congressional District 4, home to the complexes of Alto Broadcasting System and Chronicle Broadcasting Network (ABS-CBN) Corporation and Global Media Arts (GMA) Network, Incorporated, which can be both found in Timog Avenue and Mother Ignacia, respectively. However, there are also other TV stations and radio stations that are not under these two companies. These television and radio stations include Altermidya, Bitag Multimedia Network, ZOE TV (now A2Z and partnered with ABS-CBN), Jimmy Dee TV Radio International, K5 Digital Media, Mossimo Radio, TriMedia, Shepherd's Voice Radio & Television Foundation, Inc., and Star Radio Manila. The Department of Science and Technology (DOST) also has their TV stations and channels that are operating digitally and on television, where they are stationed in their compound located in Agham Road. Some of their shows include DOSTv, Panahon.TV, and Siyensikat, which is aired in GTV, another channel that is owned by GMA. Aside from that, the local government also has their own communications team on their own, hence the stations of Radyo QC 990 AM, Radyo QC 1422 AM, Radyo QC 1494 AM, Quezon City Special Reports, Busy QC, Kwentong QC, Kwentong QC Shorts, and Usapang QC can be found in the official media page of the Quezon City Government. Although ABS-CBN is now an extinct network, their transmitters are still very much active, and are being used by other channels, particularly A2Z and ANC, another company that is owned by ABS-CBN.

The influence of the GMA and the ABS-CBN complex in this part of the district led to their places be flocked on by businesses, such as the food stalls, restaurants, automobile service shops, hotels, and bars. This is also because the Triangle Park area in Diliman (where these two are located) are the home of middle-class and upper-class families and is also the spot where travel is simply accessible since EDSA can be easily traversed when respondents of

news stations are going from place to place. These two complexes are also near the North EDSA area and Cubao, respectively – which means that covering traffic jams and the situations of train lines of MRT can be easily probed and described on the news. As these two are also near each other, freelancers in the field can easily switched between these two companies, or sometimes even work for both companies. The district is also home to the Philippine Amateur Radio Association (PARA), which can be found in BIR Road, and a PLDT Office located in East Avenue.

View of GMA Building from Timog Avenue, with the logo of the company and the communication tower in the photo. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

The cover photo of ABS-CBN Integrated News and Current Affairs (Source: ABS-CBN Integrated News and Current Affairs Facebook Page)

The Novaliches area, or the Congressional District 5, has only one important station of influence, which is the site of TV5 in Quirino Highway, which is still operating, although they have moved out to Mandaluyong City. The Novaliches District also has small radio stations, such as Scouts Royale Brotherhood International Radio, Wired on Wednesday, and RADYONG MASA Entertainment Net Radio. The Novaliches District is also home to Bayan Telecommunications, which is also located in Quirino Highway, before they were brought out by Globe Telecommunications.

The studio and transmitter building of TV5 in San Bartolome in Novaliches. The station has already moved in Mandaluyong, but the transmitter is still in use for transmitting their shows and radio stations. (Source: Zachary de Castro Siriban)

The last of the districts, Congressional District 6, is home to the Iglesia ni Cristo (INC) Central Temple and the INC Complex. Being the largest non-Catholic group in the country, the INC has a wide network of radio stations and television channels under their name, which include Christian Era Broadcasting Service International (CEBSI) Incorporated, Iglesia ni Cristo TV, and Eagle Broadcasting Corporation (EBC), under the name Net 25. The district also hosts the Tower of Power of GMA, which is the network transmitter for the television channels and radio frequencies by the company. The district is also home to other productions such as Austreamers 69.69 and Kodao Productions.

Facade of the Net 25 Studio (Source: Reimybe Dalida Buhat)

Net 25 Cover Photo (Source: Net 25 Facebook Page)

Aside from the districts, there are other sources of media in the city, which are academic institutions. Every school in the city has their own journalism club or journalism group, along with a corresponding television or radio program that are used for journalism purposes, where they are usually presented in school press conferences from their respective districts up to the national level. Shown in the tables below are the different radio and television stations that can be found in the city.

Name	Type	Description
------	------	-------------

<p>REPUBLIKA FM1 87.5 FM</p>	Radio Station	Owned by the Government
<p>Capital FM2 104.3 FM</p>	Radio Station	Owned by the Government
<p>Crossover 105.1 FM</p>	Radio Station	Internet-based
<p>Q Radio 105.1 FM</p>	Radio Station	Privately Owned
<p>Wish 107.5 FM</p>	Radio Station	Privately Owned
<p>Radyo Pilipinas AM 738</p>	Radio Station	Owned by the Government
<p>Radyo Pilipinas AM 918</p>	Radio Station	Owned by the Government
<p>Radyo Veritas AM 846</p>	Radio Station	Privately Owned

<p>Radyo Veritas Asia</p>	Radio Station	Privately Owned
<p>Dominican Students' Media Center Philippines</p>	Radio Station	Privately Owned
<p>Nomixx Online Radio</p>	Radio Station	Internet-based
<p>AESTHETIC MOA FM</p>	Radio Station	Internet-based
<p>Inquirer Radyo 990 AM</p>	Radio Station	Privately Owned
<p>Now Radio AM 1098</p>	Radio Station	Privately Owned
<p>ACI News Radio AM 1170 (Radyo Pilipino)</p>	Radio Station	Privately Owned

<p>ACI News Radio AM 1206</p>	Radio Station	Privately Owned
<p>ACI News Radio AM 1278</p>	Radio Station	Defunct
<p>Banahaw Broadcasting Corporation</p>	Television Station	Defunct
<p>Radio Philippines Network</p>	Television Station	Replaced with CNN Philippines
<p>Intercontinental Broadcasting Corporation (IBC)</p>	Television Station	Nearly Closing
<p>FYA Radio</p>	Radio Station	Internet-based
	Radio Station	Internet-based

V81 Radio		
<p>DWDD AFP Radio 1134 AM</p>	Radio Station	Owned by the Government
<p>Knowledge Channel</p>	Television Channel	Privately Owned
<p>Pinoy Interactive Entertainment</p>	Television Channel	Privately Owned
<p>DZMM Teleradyo</p>	Television Channel	Privately Owned
<p>ABS-CBN NEWS CHANNEL ABS-CBN News Channel</p>	Television Channel	Privately Owned
<p>Cine Mo!</p>	Television Channel	Defunct
<p>Cinema One</p>	Television Channel	Privately Owned
<p>The Filipino Channel</p>	Television Channel	Privately Owned

<p>ASIANOVELA CHANNEL</p> <p>Asianovela Channel</p>	Television Channel	Defunct
<p>Jeepney TV</p>	Television Channel	Defunct
<p>Movie Central</p>	Television Channel	Defunct
<p>Myx Philippines</p>	Television Channel	Defunct
<p>Yey!</p>	Television Channel	Defunct
<p>Kapamilya Box Office</p>	Television Channel	Defunct
<p>O Shopping</p>	Television Channel	Defunct
<p>ABS-CBN Sports and Action</p>	Television Channel	Defunct

<p>Studio 23</p>	<p>Television Channel</p>	<p>Defunct</p>
<p>Balls TV</p>	<p>Television Station</p>	<p>Defunct</p>
<p>Cge TV</p>	<p>Television Station</p>	<p>Defunct</p>
<p>HERO</p>	<p>Television Station</p>	<p>Defunct</p>
<p>Lifestyle Channel</p>	<p>Television Station</p>	<p>Replaced by Metro Channel</p>
<p>Liga TV</p>	<p>Television Station</p>	<p>Defunct</p>
<p>MAXXX</p>	<p>Television Station</p>	<p>Defunct</p>
<p>Velvet</p>	<p>Television Station</p>	<p>Defunct</p>
<p>Tag</p>	<p>Television Station</p>	<p>Defunct</p>

<p>AN ABS-CBN STATION MOR 101.9 FM</p>	Radio Station	Defunct
<p>DZBB Super Radyo</p>	Television Channel and Radio Station	Privately Owned
<p>Barangay LS 97.1 FM</p>	Radio Station	Privately Owned
<p>GMA Network</p>	Television Station	Privately Owned
<p>GMA Life TV</p>	Television Channel	Privately Owned
<p>GMA Pinoy TV</p>	Television Channel	Privately Owned
<p>GTV</p>	Television Channel	Privately Owned
<p>Hallypop</p>	Television Channel	Privately Owned

<p>Heart of Asia Channel</p>	<p>Television Channel</p>	<p>Privately Owned</p>
<p>I Heart Movies</p>	<p>Television Channel</p>	<p>Privately Owned</p>
<p>CNN Philippines</p>	<p>Television Station</p>	<p>Privately Owned</p>
<p>Salaam TV</p>	<p>Television Channel</p>	<p>Owned by the Government</p>
<p>DepEd TV</p>	<p>Television Channel</p>	<p>Owned by the Government</p>
<p>ABS-CBN ABS-CBN</p>	<p>Television Station</p>	<p>Defunct</p>
	<p>Television Channel</p>	<p>Internet-based</p>

Living Asia Channel		
 RADYO 5 92.3 NEWSFM Radyo5 92.3 News FM	Radio Station	Privately Owned
 TV5 Channel	Television Channel	Privately Owned
 ONE Sports	Television Channel	Privately Owned
 ONE PH	Television Channel	Privately Owned
 ONE News	Television Channel	Privately Owned
 BuKo (Buhay Komedy)	Television Channel	Privately Owned
 Sari Sari Channel	Television Channel	Privately Owned

<p>PBA Rush</p>	<p>Television Channel</p>	<p>Privately Owned</p>
<p>UAAP Varsity Channel</p>	<p>Television Channel</p>	<p>Privately Owned</p>
<p>Scouts Royale Brotherhood International Radio</p>	<p>Radio Station</p>	<p>Internet-based</p>
<p>Wired on Wednesday</p>	<p>Radio Station</p>	<p>Internet-based</p>
<p>RADYO NG MASA Entertainment Net Radio</p>	<p>Radio Station</p>	<p>Internet-based</p>
<p>Altermidya</p>	<p>Television Channel</p>	<p>Internet-based</p>

			Television Channel	Privately Owned
Bitag Multimedia Network				
			Television Channel	Privately Owned
ZOE TV (Now A2Z)				
			Television Channel and Radio Station	Privately Owned
Jimmy Dee TV Radio International				
			Television Channel	Internet-based
K5 Digital Media				
			Radio Station	Privately Owned
Mossimo Radio				
			Radio Station	Privately Owned
8 TriMedia				

	<p>Shepherd's Voice Radio and TV Foundation Inc.</p>	<p>Shepherd's Voice Radio & Television Foundation, Incorporated</p>	<p>Television Channel and Radio Station</p>	<p>Privately Owned</p>
	<p>Star Radio Manila</p>		<p>Radio Station</p>	<p>Privately Owned</p>
	<p>DOSTv</p>		<p>Television Channel</p>	<p>Owned by the Government</p>
	<p>Panahon.TV</p>		<p>Television Channel</p>	<p>Owned by the Government</p>
	<p>Siyensikat</p>		<p>Television Channel</p>	<p>Owned by the Government</p>
	<p>Radyo QC 990 AM</p>		<p>Radio Station</p>	<p>Owned by the Local Government</p>
			<p>Radio Station</p>	<p>Owned by the Local Government</p>

<p>Radyo QC 1422 AM</p>		
<p>Radyo QC 1494 AM</p>	<p>Radio Station</p>	<p>Owned by the Local Government</p>
<p>Quezon City Special Reports</p>	<p>Television Channel</p>	<p>Owned by the Local Government</p>
<p>Busy QC</p>	<p>Television Channel</p>	<p>Owned by the Local Government</p>
<p>Usapang QC</p>	<p>Television Channel</p>	<p>Owned by the Local Government</p>
<p>Kwentong QC</p>	<p>Television Channel</p>	<p>Owned by the Local Government</p>
<p>Kwentong QC Shorts</p>	<p>Television Channel</p>	<p>Owned by the Local Government</p>
<p>Christian Era Broadcasting Service International (CEBSI) Incorporated</p>	<p>Television Channel</p>	<p>Privately Owned</p>

<p>INC TV</p>	Television Channel	Privately Owned
<p>Eagle Broadcasting Corporation (EBC)</p>	Television Station	Privately Owned
<p>Austreamers 69.69</p>	Radio Station	Internet-based
<p>Kodao Productions</p>	Television Channel	Privately Owned
<p>Puyat Broadcasting Corporation (PBC) 103.1 FM</p>	Radio Station	Internet-based
<p>Net 25</p>	Television Channel	Privately Owned

<p>DZUP 1602</p>		Radio Station	Backed by an Academic Institution
<p>Radyo Katipunan 87.9 FM</p>		Radio Station	Backed by an Academic Institution
<p>Radio MC</p>		Radio Station	Backed by an Academic Institution
<p>TVUP</p>		Television Channel	Backed by an Academic Institution
<p>AMAES TV</p>		Television Channel	Backed by an Academic Institution
<p>DZQC</p>		Radio Station	Backed by an Academic Institution

Martial Law Era

As the former president dictator Ferdinand Marcos Sr. announced Martial Law in September 23, 1972, the capital is subject to a lot of changes during the regime. Being the spot for many government institutions as well as being the home of the biggest broadcast companies, it is obvious that whoever controls the media is also in charge of major part of the state. This is what the dictator did, with his rule under martial law brought his cronies to the scene and take over the people that he deemed to be as enemies, such as the Lopezes. This feud with Lopezes started out as a backlash within the two families that are not in good relations with each other as both families see each other as rivals in controlling the state of the nation. Which is further solidified by the arrest of Eugenio Lopez Jr. and Amando Doronila in their print media outlet, the Manila Chronicle. Alongside with arrests of Lopez Jr. and Doronila are the arrests of Joaquin “Chino” Roces and Maximo Soliven, Roces was the former owner of the Manila Times and the founder of the Associated Broadcasting Corporation, which we now know as TV5. Soliven would also become the founder of the Philippine Star, one of the largest newspaper companies in the country as of today. With the Lopezes gone, the cronies of the administration began to take hold and control the equipment of ABS-CBN, which is seen with the introduction of Banahaw Broadcasting Corporation (BBC).

Ferdinand Marcos Sr. with his vice president, Fernando Lopez. Lopez would then be abdicated in his seat as the vice president as Marcos removes the position of vice president during his announcement of Martial Law, as well as having his family business be weakened with the looting of the cronies of the Marcoses.

(Source: Ateneo Martial Law Museum)

Along with these major players that are based in the city, Marcos would also go out of his way to control the press by shutting down eight major English newspapers, 66 TV channels,

20 radio stations, 292 provincial radio stations, 60 community newspapers, and 18 vernacular, Spanish, and English language dailies. Along with these are the arrest of thousands of journalists and government critics, many of which are integral to the development of journalism within the country during those times. These unfortunate set of events is also the reason why there is a lot of Filipino lost media that has been lost throughout the time of Martial Law during the Marcos regime, as the administration almost destroyed a lot of evidence that might even pin the down more if it was shared to the Filipinos as well as to the world.

Juan L. Mercado, one of the journalists that were arrested during Martial Law.
(Source: Cebu Journalism and Journalists)

Many events regarding the Martial Law is also caused by the involvement of the University of the Philippines in Diliman, which famously include the writings of Abraham “Ditto” Sarmiento Jr. and his lines of *“Kung hindi tayo kikilos? Kung di tayo kikibo, sino ang kikibo? Kung hindi ngayon, kailan pa?”*.

Bantayog ng Mga Bayani in Quezon City, which shows up the name of Abraham “Ditto” Sarmiento Jr. (Source: Wikimedia Photos)

The cover page of the Philippine Collegian, the university publication of the University of the Philippines in Diliman in the year 1975, written by Abraham “Ditto” Sarmiento Jr. (Source: Bulatlat, Manila Today)

Eugenio “Geny” Lopez Jr. in a hunger strike during Martial Law. (Source: ANCX)

Towards the End of a Century

After the first People Power Revolution, also known as EDSA 1, major changes in the entertainment districts of Quezon City happened, including the downfall of the Broadcast City, which is under the City2 Television (formerly Banahaw Broadcasting Corporation or BBC 2), the return of the Lopezes in the airwaves and in the small screen, and the overall improvement of the country in accepting mass media without censorship from the Marcoses. But most importantly, the age of computing is hitting to the shelves of stores and more Filipinos are affording them, especially in the areas in NCR. Starting first with the events after the end of the Marcos regime, the transfer of the transmissions under the call signs of DWWX-TV (the call sign of the former channel ABS-CBN 2) and DWWK-FM 101.9 (now called with the call sign of DWRR 101.9 before the loss of ABS-CBN's franchising). This transfer happened after the confiscating and seizing of the broadcast materials found in Benedicto's Broadcast City and was overlooked by the transition government of former President Corazon Aquino and the newly formed Presidential Commission on Good Government (abbreviated as PCGG). After this, the BBC 2 and City2 television is now replaced back again with ABS-CBN, which will then be back again as one of the dominators in terms of televising news and entertainment within the country, along with its competitor, GMA 7.

Roberto Salas Benedicto, a sugar landlord and notable crony of the Marcoses, along with his channels, the Banahaw Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) and the City2 Television.

(Source: Tita de Bacolod, Mr. JA)

As a crony during the regime, it is revealed that during the prime of his career, his assets are consisted of 85 corporations, 106 sugar farms, 14 haciendas, other agricultural lands, 17 radio stations, 16 television stations, two telecommunications networks, seven buildings, ten vessels and five aircraft. Along with that, he owned 14 hectares of real estate in Bacolod City, 13.5 billion shares in Oriental Petroleum, and membership shares in golf and country clubs estimated at US\$491,000. He has also assets in other countries, which include a sugar mill in Venezuela, a trading company in Madrid, bank deposits, mansions, and limousines in California. All this wealth is said to peak to about \$800 million, according to accounts made

by the presidential executive assistant during that time, Juan Tavera, wife of distinguished Filipina writer Kerima Polotan-Tavera. Accounting for inflation, this costs around \$2,378,883,534.14 as of today's value, or about Php 140,223,289,919.88. While Benedicto is known for his legacy in seizing Channel 2, he is also a name of a barangay in the city of La Carlota in Negros Occidental according to the website, PhilAtlas.

Compilation of former ABS-CBN Bumpers that is animated using Scanimate technology.
(Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

However, ABS-CBN have adopted the technologies which was implemented during the reign of Benedicto's dominance over the channel previously owned by the Lopezes, although of course this is because he was a very close friend and frat mate of Marcos during his time at the University of the Philippines in Diliman. This technology is called Scanimate, which is also used in the different bumpers and animations of ABS-CBN up until the 2000's, where it is both used in conjunction with computer generated graphics that are being used in other shows. Other channels have also used Scanimate to generate real-time animations in their shows, such as Radyo Pilipinas Network (RPN) Channel 9, Intercontinental Broadcasting Corporation (ICBC) Channel 13, People's Television Network (PTV) Channel 4, and Global Media Arts (GMA) Channel 7. Aside from the changes in the television scene in the country, the emergence of more consumer-friendly computer products has increased in the country, as well as second generation cellular networks, which is also known as 2G, which increased the number of mobile cellphone users in the country. Even if not asking anyone today, most people have known or have interacted with a 2G device, although there are richer families that might have been connected already with 0G (zero generation) and 1G (first generation) technologies, most of which are only accessible to the richer families during the time of the Marcos regime. Accounts for the 0G and 1G technologies in the Philippines are rare, in which the author cannot comprehend or find a decent timeline or a reference to inspect these analog radio communications, with the only exception being that of computers, like International Business Machines, also known as IBM, which proliferated during the time of the Marcos administration, as it was the standard for government agencies as well the University of the Philippines Computer Center, which is located in the Diliman area.

Compilation of former GMA Bumpers that is animated using Scanimate technology.
 (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Compilation of former RPN 9 and IBC 13 Bumpers that is animated using Scanimate technology. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Computing had a slow start in the Philippines, starting only with the Pacific Commercial Company of Manila in the year 1920, where they ordered from the Computing-Tabulating-Recording Company (abbreviated as CTR), with tabulating machines, which will then be renamed International Business Machines Corporation (abbreviated as IBM). Although these machines are tabulating ones, so they are not considered as a full-fledged computing unit. In 1953, almost three decades when they entered the Philippine market, IBM introduced its local manufacturing plant in Manila. The first of the computers to exist in the Philippines as a real computer is the introduction of the IBM 650, which is installed at the Bureau of Lands to handle land surveying. This is followed by the IBM 1401 used by the Philippine American Life Insurance Company (abbreviated as PHILAM Life) as well as the Social Security Commission (now known as the Social Security System). Other companies followed through such as the Ysmel Steel Manufacturing Company and the Central Azucarera de Tarlac.

Colorized photograph of the first IBM 650 in the Philippines, used in the Bureau of Lands for land surveying. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

The first computer unit in an academic institution is the IBM 1620 installed in the MAPUA Institute of Technology (now known as MAPUA University), and IBM continued to push through the education sector with the introduction of the Education and Data Processing (EDP) center. The System 360 units of IBM were introduced in 1966, and a Magnetic Tape / Selective Composer was introduced and inaugurated by former First Lady Imelda R. Marcos. At the same time, the University of the Philippines in Diliman introduces the University of the Philippines Computer Center, where they launched it with an IBM System 360 Model 40. Up until 1976, the IBM have received numerous orders from different companies and institutions in the Philippines, which include their System 370 systems and the IBM 4300 series. With the transition of the new government starting with Corazon

Aquino, the company has moved in to introduce Automated Telling Machines or ATMs in the Bank of the Philippine Islands (abbreviated as BPI) with their IBM 3624. At this point, more computer companies in the Philippines emerged, but IBM was still the standard for industrial machines, until the widespread introduction of personal computing units in the country. In this point in time, the era of disk operating systems or DOS begin to pop up.

Colorized photograph of the staff of the Bureau of Lands, now known as the Bureau of Lands Management. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Colorized photograph of the staff of the University of the Philippines Computer Center. (Source: University of the Philippines Computer Center)

```

1 PROGRAM CMLXLD
2 IMPLICIT COMPLEX(X)
3 PARAMETER (PI = 3.141592653589793238462643, XJ = (0, 1))
4 DO 1, I = 0, 23
5     X = EXP(XJ * I * PI / 6)
6     IF (AIMAG(X).LT.0) THEN
7         PRINT 2, 'e**(j*', I, '*pi/6) = ', REAL(X), ' - j', -AIMAG(X)
8     ELSE
9         PRINT 2, 'e**(j*', I, '*pi/6) = ', REAL(X), ' + j', AIMAG(X)
10    END IF
11    2 FORMAT (A, I1, A, F10.7, A, F9.7)
12    1 CONTINUE
13 STOP
14 END

```

```

e**(j*0*pi/6) = 1.0000000 + j0.0000000
e**(j*1*pi/6) = 0.8660254 + j0.5000000
e**(j*2*pi/6) = 0.5000000 + j0.8660254
e**(j*3*pi/6) = -0.0000000 + j1.0000000
e**(j*4*pi/6) = -0.5000001 + j0.8660254
e**(j*5*pi/6) = -0.8660255 + j0.4999998
e**(j*6*pi/6) = -1.0000000 - j0.0000001
e**(j*7*pi/6) = -0.8660253 - j0.5000002
e**(j*8*pi/6) = -0.4999999 - j0.8660254
e**(j*9*pi/6) = 0.0000000 - j1.0000000
e**(j*10*pi/6) = 0.5000004 - j0.8660252
e**(j*11*pi/6) = 0.8660256 - j0.4999998
e**(j*12*pi/6) = 1.0000000 + j0.0000002
e**(j*13*pi/6) = 0.8660254 + j0.5000001
e**(j*14*pi/6) = 0.4999996 + j0.8660256
e**(j*15*pi/6) = 0.0000001 + j1.0000000
e**(j*16*pi/6) = -0.5000002 + j0.8660253
e**(j*17*pi/6) = -0.8660254 + j0.4999999
e**(j*18*pi/6) = -1.0000000 - j0.0000000
e**(j*19*pi/6) = -0.8660254 - j0.4999999
e**(j*20*pi/6) = -0.4999993 - j0.8660258
e**(j*21*pi/6) = 0.0000007 - j1.0000000
e**(j*22*pi/6) = 0.5000005 - j0.8660251
e**(j*23*pi/6) = 0.8660251 - j0.5000004
e**(j*24*pi/6) = 1.0000000 + j0.0000003

```

An example of a computer screen running IBM's FORTRAN. In this code, it writes out the complex numerical values of $e^{ji\pi/6}$ from the values of the variable i from 0 to 23 and with j as the imaginary number, $\sqrt{-1}$. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

The origin of DOS personal computers begins with the introduction of the DOS 1.0 in 1981, which is meant for the IBM line of personal computers. A few years after, DOS 3.0 was introduced in April 1985, where it introduced support for local area networks (abbreviated as LAN's). At this point, IBM PC Compatibles are also existing in the market, in which they are not manufactured by IBM, but made their computers to be as similar as the IBM line to create a competition in the booming computer market in the 80's. DOS would be popular in the computing scene up until the introduction of Windows 95, and a few years later, the introduction of Mac OS 8, although the operating system scene was heavily dominated by Microsoft as Apple is facing a crisis during the time, hence the reason why Microsoft has entered and penetrated the computing market to the public much earlier. For countries like the Philippines, this means that computers will all be based on the Microsoft computer operating system. DOS is known to be popular to college students of the Philippines during the 90's, and with the introduction of a more user-friendly operating system such as that of the '95 line up to the Millenium Edition, many people are slowly entering the era of computers. Although more people will be introduced first to mobile communications before the time of computing

and the Internet. Nowadays, cellphones with a keypad are rare, but they can still be found in cellphone repair shops in the city. These keypad phones have existed from the year 1987, which is made possible by Philippine Long Distance Telephone Company or PLDT, for long up until 2015, where Android phones are catching up to more features and capabilities that keypad phones cannot do.

```

READY .
NEW
READY .
FOR L=1 TO 20:PRINT L*3.14159265: NEXT L
3.14159265
6.283185307
9.424777961
12.566370614
15.707963268
18.849555922
21.991148669
25.132741411
28.274333333
31.415926536
34.557519119
37.699111818
40.840704444
43.982299711
47.123888999
50.265482224
53.407169555
56.548666777
59.690252223
62.831853
READY .
RUN
READY .

```

An example of a computer screen running BASIC. In this code, it writes out the numerical values of the multiples of pi. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

An example of a local Windows command line doing a legacy command from a DOS system, which is used to change color as well as to locate file attributes. In removable disk drives placed in a universal serial bus or USB port, this can be used to locate malicious software or malware, located in the drive. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Closer than Ever

As technology is also hitting in the Philippines market like crazy after the year 2000, television in the country have also started to introduce more complex computer animations in replacement of the Scanimate edits using computer units. This is evident with shows that are being generated using computers or is being used alongside with models, which is present in movies that are produced during the 2000's. But 2G mobile phone technology is still present in the country even with the introduction of the different products that will be the predecessors of the smartphones that almost all Filipinos have now today. A lot of promotional materials for television shows were also done by utilizing 2G cellular phone technology, as well as voting for people television reality shows or talents shows. Although this practice is still being done by such shows, it isn't as much as impactful as that of before as the internet started to become more and more popular in the Philippine scene. As a larger contributor of these things happening within the area of the city, Quezon City is known for promoting media within private and government institutions within it.

Mobile cellular phone repair shops in Commonwealth Market in Quezon City.
(Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Along with these, prominent computer companies have evolved further their technology as well as their grasp in the Philippine market, as well as the introduction of faster and better technologies that have entered the country while being also affected by the globalization of all things and the openness of resources that are hard to find that are now being published on the Internet. In the year 2013, it is stated by the MEC Networks Corporation that the number of mobile number subscribers in the Philippines have reached up to 102 million, and that of the next year, the Philippines is named as the country with the fastest growing internet population in the last five years with a growth of 531%, and that 38% of Filipinos have used technologies that are related to the Internet. In 2017, all these technologies have connected more people with the reports stating that a greater percentage of broadband subscription is now accessible to the lowest broadband plans, with almost 80% of them at least avails that lowest

subscription plans. After the fall of 2G technologies comes the introduction of the 3G up to 5G technology, which includes technologies of mobile networks that have also access to the Internet.

Timeslots of evening shows by ABS-CBN in the year 2002. (Source: Oskee Media)

A program advisory of ABS-CBN in the year 2002. (Source: Oskee Media)

A text promo of the show, “Aqua Bendita” in the year 2010, which is participated by the viewing audience of the show. (Source: ABS-CBN Entertainment)

With the rise of internet technologies in the Philippines, the Philippine society becomes slowly engrained with the use of web applications and websites in which people have the power to communicate better with the use of computers and evolved radio technologies, with 3G now evolving into 4G and 5G technologies. Popular websites in the Philippines are those that can be used for social communication and video sharing, such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, TikTok, etc.

Ironic Comeback: former TV show host of ABS-CBN Willie Revillame now hosts a show from ALLTV. ALLTV is the replacement of ABS-CBN after a problem that involves the Philippine government. (Source: ALLTV YouTube Channel)

The evolution of the user interface (UI) of the website Twitter, a popular social media website in the Philippines. (Source: Internet Archive, Twitter)

Communication of Younger QCitizens

Quezon City's importance in establishing communication within the country is undeniably one of its charms, along with the landmarks and historical markers that it has within it. Whether this allure caught up to the younger generation of the city can only be found out by directly asking them by also surveying them directly. In this part of the paper, the author identified out to do a survey on his former high school, Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School. Formerly a branch of the city's original public high school, Quezon City High School,

which is in Kamuning, Cubao High School became an integral part of the schooling of thousands of alumni in the Cubao and other areas in the city, some of which are far flung up and are still schooling there because the school is known for both academic and extracurricular activities that are happening within there. When the former president Ramon Magsaysay died in a plane crash in Cebu, the school is honored to have the name of the former president alongside with another school located in Ermita, Manila.

SunStar Davao

sunstar.com.ph/davao

Overall Google Search Trends in the year 2021. (Source: Google, Sunstar Davao)

As a former student of the said school, the author decided to investigate on how important communication to the more coherent people there, which are the students of the Senior High School Department. Divided into four strands, STEM, ABM, GAS, and HUMSS (which was introduced after the former TVL Tracks was given to Fernando C. Amorsolo Senior High School in Kamuning), the population of the students in the Senior High School department is sizable enough to fit in into this survey. In this short survey section that was made using Google Forms, a tool made by Google to quickly generate forms and to send and answer it by a specific number of people, a total of (number) students have been able to answer the following questions, which is a sizable portion of their student population which is % of the whole student department. The demographics of the respondents in the survey are shown in the figures below:

Respondents

Demographics

Graphical representation of the demographics of the respondents of the survey that was conducted by the author. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Because some data that was collected were sensitive, the author redacted them after tabulating in accordance with the provisions of Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012, in which the author stated in the Google Form that only those involved in the current study will have access to their given information and the exchange of which will be facilitated through online means. The collected data from the online survey shows that the gender distribution of the students that were asked comprises of 35.7% male respondents, 40.2% female respondents, 18.9% of the respondents belong to the LGBTQI+ community, and 5.2% of the respondents prefer not to say their gender. Out of all the 250 respondents that have been

asked in the senior high school program, 17.3% of them belong to Grade 11 STEM, 4.0% belong to Grade 11 ABM, 12.9% belong to Grade 11 HUMSS, and 10.0% of them belong to Grade 11 GAS. In the case of the Grade 12 students, 19.7% belong to Grade 12 STEM, 20.5% belong to Grade 12 ABM, 8.0% belong to Grade 12 HUMSS, and 7.6% belong to Grade 12 GAS. Variation of the used devices by these students tallied at tablets being the least owned, with a count of 84 students said to have tablets, followed by desktop computers, which account for 99 students. As laptops and smartphones are common for the students, more have said that they have one in their homes, with a count of 152 students saying that they have laptops at home, and almost all students have smartphones, which 213 students said to have one.

Respondents

Demographics

Graphical representation of the demographics of the respondents of the survey that was conducted by the author. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Respondents

Demographics

Graphical representation of the demographics of the respondents of the survey that was conducted by the author. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

For the connectivity of these devices, 197 students stated that they use their own home internet connection, while 146 use mobile data for their connectivity. Other options for connectivity include internet cafes with 97 students, nearby establishments, or public places with 71, apartment or dormitory connections with 19, and the usage of the neighbor's internet connection peaking at 11. Most of the respondents admitted that they use their devices for more than six hours, with 106 respondents, some of the respondents only hang out for four to six hours, with 91, a few just peek in for about one to three hours, with 46 respondents, and six people stated that they only use it for less than an hour. For the social media communication devices that they use, all the students have access to Google's services as well as their Facebook

accounts, this is followed by their other accounts, such as Twitter, Instagram, TikTok, and Discord. Snapchat, CuriousCat, and Telegram appeared to be familiar for some, and a collective of students know other social messaging and communication applications such as WhatsApp, Tumblr, Viber, Yahoo, and Pinterest. A notable few students know Omegle and Ask.FM. In the survey, no one used Tinder, Bumble, and VKontakte, which are lesser-known social media applications in the country.

Responses

Survey Questions

LEGEND

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

QUESTIONS

1. With the presence of many social media platforms, do you still use your short messaging service (SMS) application in smartphones for personal communication?
2. Is social media presence a consideration when doing your personal activities?
3. As you have returned back to your face-to-face classes, is social media presence still a major consideration when doing your academic activities?
4. Would you say that being active social media influences your goals in life?
5. Do you believe that being the "City of Stars", Quezon City must be a role model for improving the communication for every Filipino?
6. Do you agree pandemic affected the effectivity and / or range of communication and mass media within the city during the past two years?
7. As a student of a public high school within the city, do you believe that Quezon City is doing well in disseminating information to its constituents?
8. Do you believe that being immersed in social media made contacting the city's different departments easier to the residents?

ANSWERS

Graphical representation of the survey questions answered by the respondents conducted by the author. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

As for the responses, there are eight questions that have been answered by the respondents in this short survey. Question #1 inquires if the respondents are still using their short messaging system messaging in their phones, which are met with the responses of “Yes” with 57.8%, “No” with 35.3%, and “Maybe” with 6.8%. Question #2 investigates if social media presence is important for their personal activities in life, which are met with the responses of “Yes” with 60.2%, “No” with 29.3%, and “Maybe” with 10.4%. Question #3 asks the same as stated in the question in Question #2, but in terms of their academic activities, these are met with the responses of “Yes” with 60.7%, “No” with 28.8%, and “Maybe” with 10.5%. Question #4 asks the respondents if they would consider that social media influences their lgoals in life, which is answered with “Yes” with 55.7%, “No” with 16.2%, and “Maybe” with 28.1%. Question #5 is related to the moniker of the city being the “City of Stars”, and that if Quezon City must be a role model for improving the communication of every Filipino, this is answered by the respondents with “Yes” with 63.5%, “No” with 17.3%, and “Maybe” with 19.3%. Question #6 asks if the current coronavirus pandemic affected the effectivity and range of communication of mass media within the years that have passed since the pandemic, which is replied with “Yes” with 62.6%, “No” with 13.0%, and “Maybe” with 24.3%. Question #7 asks if the local government of Quezon City is doing well in disseminating information to its constituents inside the city, especially with their case as a student of a public high school, which is replied with “Yes” with 45.3%, “No” with 14.8%, and “Maybe” with 39.9%. Lastly, Question #8 asks if the local government of Quezon City made access to their services easier with the introduction and immersion of online media to their services, which is replied with “Yes” with 60.6%, “No” with 10.4%, and “Maybe” with 28.9%.

Discussion

This paper shows how important is Quezon City is being one of the frontiers in the development of communication in the whole country. While not being that much active in print media, as the companies who do print in the city are parts of a bigger company, such as the case of ABS-CBN, the city is pretty much active in advocating the field of mass media communication and telecommunication in the city, evident with the abundance of business process outsourcing (BPO) call centers. However, the city’s main highlight is the presence of media companies, whether big or small or even owned by the national government. This is the reason why the city is called the “City of Stars”.

It is also seen with the responses of the students in the short survey that was conducted by the author that majority of the students have already engrained the use of social media into their lives and know the importance of integrating these modern methods of communication to their lives, whether it is personally or academically. Results in the survey show that all of them are affected mostly by social communication and blogging applications and the services that is provided by Google, which includes their email service under Google Mail and their video sharing site under YouTube. For this short survey it is to be included that most of the younger demographic specifically to Quezon City is using products made by the companies Meta, which is the company of Facebook, and Alphabet, the main company of Google. The respondents of the survey can be also said to be also aware of the transition and migration of the Quezon City local government into online, along with their services, but some of them are still not that aware of these changes, as they may have been preoccupied with school activities or hangouts with their friends. A lot of the young respondents too know a lot of social media sites aside from

Facebook and Google, which include other popular social media communication sharing sites such as Twitter, Instagram, TikTok, and Discord. Aside for Instagram which is also owned by Meta, the other three might have been used by students to ensure other means of communications socially, which may avoid them from just being stuck with their Facebook accounts.

A cover of the magazines Metro (left) and Maxim (right). (Source: ABS-CBN Publishing)

UP AyalaLand TechnoHub, a BPO area in Quezon City. (Source: Ma Phi Rose)

It is also tackled how the city is formed, how did it become a sprawling area before being declared as a part of a new city and the origins of the names in the area, and how is it planned to be the capital, before being reverted into Manila due to the decree of the late dictator,

President Ferdinand Marcos Sr. The effects of Quezon City in the field of communication are plenty, and a paper like this is most likely scratching only the surface of the grand significance of the city as a discourse hub.

AFNI One Felicity Center, a BPO building in Quezon City. (Source: Sherwin Claveria)

The paper also investigated how the aspect of communication is affecting the younger generation of the constituents of the city, as well as how the city is doing with connecting with its constituents. It is apparent that the city has a great influence over communicating to the residents, but the scale of how it is being properly understood by the residents, specifically to the younger generation of the residents, needs to be catered better to the residents and to other people that are working or studying within the limits of the city.

An Attempt for a Timeline

This part of the paper concludes what have been discussed through this paper, and the author will do its best to include almost all the technologies that have been made available in the Philippines, particularly those that have been available in Quezon City. Shown below is the timeline, in which the author believes is still pragmatically incomplete, of the technologies and the improvement of said technologies in the City of Stars. This will be generalized, as the timeline of events that happened with the development of technologies will be long and will include most of the technologies that we are just using within our old television sets, smartphone screens, personal computers, and laptops.

Date	Event in Quezon City's Communication History
April 5, 1905	A certain Mrs. Redgrave, possibly Corinne Robert Redgrave, began test broadcasting from Nichols Air Field with a five-watt transmitter.
June 1, 1922	Two AM stations in Manila and Pasay are founded by Henry Hermann Sr., owner of the Manila-based Electrical Supply Company, in 1922 and

	broadcasted using a 5-watt transmitter. This is to test the potential of broadcasting in the Philippines.
1924	The AM station of Hermann Sr. boosted its power to 100 watts and renamed itself as KZKZ AM.
October 4, 1924	Hermann Sr. sells the KZKZ AM to Radio Corporation of the Philippines (RCP)
September 13-17, 1926	Time Magazine on their article reports that the announced that the Radio Corporation of the Philippines was constructing two of the largest radio stations in the Philippines with the idea of maintaining direct Manila-San Francisco service.
December 5, 1927	The Ship Radio Station Law (Act No. 3396), provided for the first radio regulatory office, known as Radio Construction and Maintenance Section to enforce radio laws and regulations, particularly the installation of radio obligatory for Philippineregistered ships to protect life and property at sea.
November 18, 1928	PLDT was established by means of a merger of four telephone companies under operation of the American telephone company General Telephone and Electronics Corporation.
December 8, 1928	Congress passed Act No. 3495 granting the Robert Dollar Company a franchise to operate wireless long-distance message services in the Philippines.
April 14, 1905	The American Insular Government of the Philippines establishes the Radio Control Board in the Philippines, which is used to regulate frequencies and licenses.
November 11, 1931	Radio Control Law of the Philippines (Act No. 3846), created the Radio Control Division under the supervision of the Secretary of Commerce and Communications.
May 3, 1933	KZRM AM is introduced.
May 8, 1933	The Americans established and operated radio station KZSO in the Philippines on the frequency of 710 kilohertz with a power of 10,000 watts through the United States Information Service.
November 28, 1934	Congress passed Act No. 4150 to transfer the franchise and privileges of the Robert Dollar Company to Globe Wireless Limited.
January 15, 1935	Globe Wireless Limited Is incorporated in the Philippines.
November 3, 1936	Commonwealth Act No. 120 is approved, creating the National Power Corporation.
July 14, 1939	Samuel Gaches, head of the H.E. Heacock Department Store, starts up KZRH.
July 15, 1939	KZRH announces its broadcast at exactly 6:00 AM in the morning with Hal Bowie speaking through the radio.
October 12, 1939	Quezon City is created under the Commonwealth Act No. 502, also known as the Charter of Quezon City, passed by the National Assembly during the Commonwealth period. The city's first mayor, the former president Manuel L. Quezon himself, is the one maintaining the city until he invited Tomas Morato in Manila.
November 1, 1939	Executive Order No. 230 formally organized the Department of National Defense (DND), transferring the Radio Control Division to it in view of the

	national defense and security aspects of the establishment and operation of radio stations in the country.
November 9, 1939	Tomas Morato, former mayor of Calauag, Tayabas (now the Province of Quezon) and close friend of former President Quezon, agrees to be part of the new city.
November 10, 1939	Former President Quezon appoints Tomas Morato, to become the first mayor of the city, where he will be retroactively effective as Mayor on October 12, even if he was signed on duty in November 10. Ponciano Bernardo becomes the vice mayor the city.
December 17, 1939	American city planner and architect, William Edward Parsons, unfortunately died in New Haven, Connecticut. The city planner for the city is then replaced by Harry T. Frost.
May 1, 1940	Harry Frost arrives in Manila as replacement of the late city planner, William Parsons.
April 24, 1905	Harry Frost, along with Juan Arellano, Alpheus Williams, Louis Croft, and Welton Becket have finished their Master Plan for Quezon City, which is also known as the Frost Plan or the Frost-Arellano Plan.
April 1, 1941	The Quezon administration, fearing the imminent threat of the second World War in the Pacific, builds the Civilian Emergency Administration (CEA).
June 21, 1941	Quezon City's boundaries were changed to revert some areas taken in Marikina as well as the Wack Wack Country and Golf Club owned by William Shaw, but Camp Murphy will be taken by Quezon City under the provisions of Commonwealth Act No. 659
August 13, 1941	The Commonwealth of the Philippines celebrated a legal holiday given under the Roosevelt administration which suspends the eight-hour day for mechanics and laborers employed by the War Department on public works projects such as airfields, troop housing units and fortifications to hasten their construction.
November 11, 1941	Manuel Quezon is re-elected again as President, winning a total of 81.78% of the total number of votes, against Senator Juan Sumulong and Hilario Moncado of the Filipino Crusaders World Army and the Equi Frili Brium Igliesiarum.
November 27, 1941	Former President of the United States Franklin D. Roosevelt passed a bill making the fourth Thursday in November the National Thanksgiving Day, which was celebrated in the States on November 26, but due to time zones the Philippine Commonwealth celebrated it on the 27th. Technically speaking, this will be the first Thanksgiving of the Commonwealth, as they entered through a series of transitions during the invasion of the Japanese forces.
December 8, 1941	Hours after the incident at Peral Harbor in Hawaii, the Imperial Japanese forces launched a surprise attack on the Philippines in the Northern parts of Luzon.
December 11, 1941	Following the pressure of the upcoming conflicts in the Philippine campaign, former President Manuel I. Quezon appoints his executive secretary, Jorge B. Vargas, to become the secretary of National Defense.
December 12, 1941	More forces arrive at the Southern parts of Luzon, particularly in the Bicol region.

December 20, 1941	The Quezon administration moved their war cabinet to Corregidor Island to avoid problems with the Imperial Japanese forces seizing the capital and the government.
December 22, 1941	Jorge B. Vargas becomes the head of the Civilian Emergency Administration, as the Imperial Japanese forces have landed in Lingayen, Pangasinan.
December 23, 1941	The Imperial Japanese forces were reported to be moving in within Pangasinan and is heading towards Manila.
December 24, 1941	Being the head of the Civilian Emergency Administration, Jorge B. Vargas becomes the first mayor of the areas in wartime Manila, later given the name of the city of Greater Manila.
December 26, 1941	Manila is declared to be an “open city” by General Douglas McArthur. This is done to prevent damages in the capital.
December 29, 1941	The Imperial Japanese forces bombed Manila, even if General McArthur declared it as an “open city”, to strip off the American and Filipino forces from using it as a strategic logistic location.
January 1, 1942	Executive Order No. 400 was formed by former President Quezon, forming the temporary city of Greater Manila, or GMA. The Imperial Japanese Army delivered a notice to Vargas that the forces temporarily camped at Parañaque would enter Greater Manila the following day.
January 2, 1942	The Imperial Japanese forces entered Manila around 9:00 to 10:00 AM, Philippine Standard Time.
January 3, 1942	General Masaharu Homma becomes the Japanese Military Governor of the Philippines, Homma declares that the American rule in the Philippines is now replaced by Imperial Japan, and Japanese Martial Law is declared in the Philippines, which includes the city of Greater Manila.
January 13, 1942	Under the law of the Imperial Japanese Army, every form of opposition is subject to Japanese death penalty.
January 23, 1942	The Philippine Executive Commission (PEC) was formed by the Imperial Japanese government, which is set up as a provisional government by the Japanese to control the Greater Manila Area and eventually the whole Philippines. The presiding officer is Chairman Jorge Vargas.
January 27, 1942	Jorge Vargas assigns Leon Guinto Sr. as the mayor of the city of Greater Manila Area.
1942-1945	Parts of the city were seized by the Imperial Japanese forces and was transformed into districts, which is composed of Balintawak, Diliman, and Caloocan. Other parts of the city during this time are still part of the Province of Rizal.
February 17, 1942	The Military Government of Japan issues an order adopting the Japanese educational system in the country.
February 20, 1942	The Quezon administration and its war cabinet leave for the United States.
March 1, 1942	With the command of General McArthur that moved the forces of the Americans and the Filipinos in Corregidor and Bataan, Greater Manila Area is subject to the Imperial Japanese forces.
March 11, 1942	General Douglas MacArthur left Corregidor which is now surrounded by the Japanese.
March 13, 1942	General McArthur heads through Mindanao and the Philippine Commonwealth is moved to the United States.

March 21, 1942	General McArthur's crew arrives in Melbourne in Australia, making his "I shall return" speech.
March 29, 1942	The Hukbong Bayan Laban sa Hapon or HUKBALAHAP was founded. While it has no effect to the history of Quezon City, they will be prominent in the future.
April 1, 1942	An unknown American resistance movement is organized, mainly used to give intelligence on the Japanese positions.
April 9, 1942	Bataan is the last area to surrender against the Imperial Japanese Army.
May 1, 1942	The Philippine Executive Commission adopts the Japanese Standard Time which moves the Philippine clock an hour ahead.
May 3, 1942	The Imperial Japanese forces start to occupy the Philippines.
May 5, 1942	The Imperial Japanese forces landed on Corregidor Island.
May 6, 1942	Corregidor falls to the Imperial Japanese Army.
May 8, 1942	Total surrender of the American and Filipino forces were accepted by the Imperial Japanese Army
June 8, 1942	General Shizuichi Tanaka replaces General Masaharu Homma as the Japanese Military Governor of the Philippines.
June 14, 1942	The Philippine Commonwealth becomes a member of the United Nations.
July 19, 1942	Tomas Morato, mayor of Quezon City, was arrested by the Imperial Japanese forces, subsequently ending his term as the mayor. Quezon City will have no mayors for the time being, and the head of Quezon City is under the command of the Greater Manila Area.
December 8, 1942	The Kapisanan ng Paglilingkod sa Bagong Pilipinas (KALIBAPI) is founded to be a Filipino version of the Japanese government via Proclamation No. 109 by Jorge Vargas.
December 30, 1942	KALIBAPI is formally inaugurated on the death anniversary of National Hero, Dr. Jose Rizal. Benigno Aquino Sr. is the director-general of the party.
May 6, 1943	Japanese Prime Minister Hideki Tojo visits the Philippines and has a ceremony held in Luneta Park
May 28, 1943	General Shigenori Kuroda replaces General Shizuichi Tanaka as the Japanese Military Governor of the Philippines.
June 20, 1943	Hideki Tojo prepares a Preparatory Commission for Philippine Independence by employing a 20-man Filipino group.
September 1, 1943	Camilo Osias replaces Benigno Aquino Sr. is the director-general of the KALIBAPI.
September 4, 1943	A new Constitution is drafted by the Philippine Preparatory Commission for Independence
September 20, 1943	The Philippine Preparatory Commission for Independence chooses the 108 members of the Philippine National Assembly
September 25, 1943	The Philippine presidential elections for the puppet Second Philippine Republic were done, with Jose P. Laurel being the chosen standard bearer

	of the KALIBAPI and is elected as the President of the Philippines, with a voter turnout of 100%.
October 14, 1943	Former President Jose P. Laurel becomes the president of the Philippines, and the puppet government is inaugurated.
November 1, 1943	Philippine economy collapses.
November 10, 1943	The United States Congress approves a resolution of former President Manuel Quezon to serve nine more days after his term expires.
December 30, 1943	Harry Frost is reported to be dead and is featured in the obituary of the New York Times.
April 1, 1944	Former President Quezon is reported to be suffering greatly from tuberculosis and is situated at a certain Miami Beach Army hospital.
May 1, 1944	As an answer to the famine problem and the crash of the Philippine economy, the puppet government starts the Green Revolution in the Philippines, which is the implementation of scientific research and current technologies during that time to improve the situation of agriculture in the country.
July 17, 1944	Leon Guinto Sr. ends his term as the second and last mayor of the city of Greater Manila Area.
August 1, 1944	Former President Quezon dies in a “cure cottage”, a type of tuberculosis sanatorium, in Saranac Lake in New York, reported to die at 10:05 AM. Former President Sergio Osmeña Sr. becomes the President of the Philippine Commonwealth.
September 21, 1944	Manila is raided by the American forces.
September 26, 1944	General Tomoyuki Yamashita replaces General Shigenori Kuroda as the Japanese Military Governor of the Philippines.
October 20, 1944	General Douglas McArthur lands in Palo, Leyte. More forces arrive in Dulag, Leyte, and starts to liberate Tacoban.
October 23, 1944	General Douglas McArthur reestablished the Philippine Commonwealth, with Former President Sergio Osmeña Sr. as the President of the Philippine Commonwealth.
December 8, 1944	General Pio Duran and General Benigno Ramos started organizing the Japanese support group, Makabayang Katipunan ng mga Pilipino (MAKAPILI). They operated mainly on the Greater Manila Area.
January 9, 1945	The US Sixth Army landed on the Gulf of Lingayen. A military radio station under the name of KZSO, is reported to be in the submarine units of the American forces and will land on Lingayen after the area is cleared of the Japanese.
February 3, 1945	The United States troops enter the outskirts of Manila, possibly areas of the Greater Manila Area, which may include parts of Rizal (Payatas and Bagong Silangan), Caloocan (Novaliches) and Quezon City (University District, Cubao, Roces Avenue).
February 4, 1945	The United States troops entered the city of Manila.
February 7, 1945	General Douglas McArthur enters the city of Manila.

February 22, 1945	The troop leaders of the Hukbong Bayan Laban sa Hapon were arrested by the American forces due to paramilitary activity. The HUKBALAHAP retired back to being labor leaders and workers.
February 24, 1945	The Japanese forces in Manila surrendered to the American and Filipino troops.
February 27, 1945	General Douglas McArthur turns over the Malacañang Palace back to the current president of the Philippine Commonwealth, Sergio Osmeña.
March 3, 1945	American and Filipino troops take back the city of Manila.
March 16, 1945	With the return of the formal military force, the paramilitary guerilla force of the Hukbong Bayan Laban sa Hapon or HUKBALAHAP established the Congress of Labor Organizations (CLO).
March 22, 1945	Pro-Japanese Filipino leaders of the Laurel administration, which include President Jose P. Laurel and Benigno Q. Aquino Sr., leave for Japan to escape the Philippines.
June 5, 1945	The First Congress of the Commonwealth of the Philippines assembles for the first time.
July 5, 1945	General Douglas McArthur announces the liberation of the Philippines.
July 26, 1945	Former President Sergio Osmeña dissolves the City of Greater Manila under Executive Order No. 58.
August 15, 1945	The Japanese Empire admits their defeat.
August 17, 1945	The Second Philippine Republic, under the leadership of former President Jose P. Laurel, is abolished by Laurel himself and thus ending his presidency.
September 12, 1945	Former President Jose P. Laurel is arrested by the American army.
December 1, 1945	The House Insular Affairs Committee of the United States Congress approved the joint resolution setting the date of the 1946 Philippine election on not later than April 30, 1946.
January 4, 1946	Commonwealth Act No. 725 is approved by the Second Congress
January 5, 1946	Commonwealth Act No. 725 is signed by former President Sergio Osmeña, thus starting the 1946 Philippine election.
January 7, 1946	News company Reuters reported that the Philippines ordered goods worth ₱1,000,000 a day from America. Imports from the United States skyrocketed, including textiles, food, and building materials, which is for postwar repairs of those that have been destroyed during the Second World War.
January 19, 1946	The Liberal Wing had senators Manuel Roxas and Elpidio Quirino as their candidates for president and vice president, which is held at the Sta. Ana Cabaret.
January 21, 1946	The Nacionalista Loyalists had President Osmeña and Senator Eulogio Rodriguez as their candidates for president and vice president, which is held at Ciro Club, Santa Mesa, Manila.
January 1, 1946	The Partido Modernista had self-proclaimed general Hilario Camino Moncado and Luis Salvador as their candidates for president and vice president.

January 31, 1946	Malacañang announced that President Sergio Osmeña will not campaign. While Roxas pushes himself more for the campaign in the presidency.
April 23, 1946	Manuel Roxas is elected as the first President of the Third Republic of the Philippines, as well as the last President of the Philippine Commonwealth.
June 13, 1946	James “Jim” Lindenberg founded the Bolinao Electronics Corporation (BEC), which is named after his wife’s hometown in Pangasinan.
July 1, 1946	HUKBALAHAP’s party, Hukbong Mapaglaya ng Bayan (HMB), is organized in Candaba, Pampanga. KZKZ AM of the Radio Corporation of the Philippines changes its name to DWKZ AM.
July 4, 1946	The United States recognizes the full independence of the Third Republic of the Philippines, with Manuel Roxas as its first president.
September 1, 1946	A makeshift studio was constructed in an old warehouse of Carmelo and Bauermann on Azcarraga Street (now Recto Avenue), which transformed KZSO into KZFM. This studio is near the Far Eastern University (FEU).
October 27, 1946	Former President Elpidio Quirino delivers a speech to the inauguration of the radio station KZFM.
December 24, 1946	Ponciano Bernardo is announced to be the mayor of Quezon City by former President Osmeña
January 1, 1947	Former mayor Ponciano Bernardo is sworn into office.
March 6, 1947	HUKBALAHAP activities are now declared as illegal
July 1, 1947	Executive Order No. 94 created the Department of Commerce and Industry, transferring to the Radio Control Division.
August 1, 1947	Francisco “Koko” Trinidad becomes the representative of the Philippines to the 1947 International Telegraph Convention, where the callsign “D” is assigned for the Philippines, as punishment for Germany to not use their own country’s callsign. This replaces the “K” callsign in the Philippines. Trinidad tried to pursue for the callsign “RP”, but is denied due to the major overhaul in revising the charter.
September 12, 1947	The Radio Broadcasting Board now took charge of the administration and operation of KZFM.
October 2, 1947	Radio and television stations in the Philippines are now required to change the first call letter from “K” to “D” with DZ standing for Luzon stations, DY for Visayas and Palawan stations, and DX for Mindanao and Sulu stations.
November 1, 1947	Postwar elections for the Third Philippine Republic is held for the local officials and senators.
January 29, 1948	Former President Manuel Roxas declares a general pardon for all those with collaboration cases in the People's Court.
March 1, 1948	Former President Manuel Roxas declares the organizations rooted from HUKBALAHAP, namely Hukbong Mapagpalaya ng Bayan and Pambansang Kaisahan ng mga Magbubukid (PKM), to be illegal.
April 15, 1948	Former President Roxas delivers a speech to the US Thirteenth Air Force at Clark Air Base, Pampanga. After the speech, he suffered multiple heart attacks and died at 9:23 PM at the age of 56.
April 17, 1948	Former Vice President Elpidio Quirino arrives at Manila and went to Malacañang and took the oath of office as president. Quirino then assigned a month of mourning for the fallen Roxas.

April 25, 1948	Sessions of the Philippine Congress are resumed after being suspended with the news of former President Roxas being dead.
July 14, 1948	By the virtue of Republic Act No. 333, the Capital City Planning Commission was established and was headed by Juan Arellano.
July 17, 1948	By the virtue of the Republic Act No. 333, Quezon City was made to be the capital of the Philippines. It also created the Capital City Planning Commission which was tasked to prepare the general development plan and supervise the improvements. This act also made the neighboring town of Caloocan to lose more barrios, which are Baesa, Bagbag, Bahay-Toro, Banlat, Novaliches, Pasong Tamo, San Bartolome and Talipapa
May 1, 1905	The Welcome Rotonda is introduced.
August 1, 1948	Under the command of Luis Taruc, the HUKBALAHAP continued to resist the government of Quirino.
October 1, 1948	Former President Elpidio Quirino releases the result of the first postwar census in the Philippines, taken and compiled by the Bureau of the Census and Statistics
November 1, 1948	The Partido Komunista ng Pilipinas or PKP, is reported to renew armed struggle following failed truce negotiations with the government
May 2, 1905	The Bolinao Electronics Coporation shifted from electronics to radio station equipment, with the introduction of DZBC AM.
March 20, 1949	DZPI AM is introduced in the airwaves.
April 28, 1949	Former First Lady Aurora Quezon with Maria Aurora Quezon, and Quezon City Mayor Ponciano Bernardo, are killed in an ambush allegedly by the HUKBALAHAP in Bongabon, Nueva Ecija. Nicanor A. Roxas now served in acting capacity as the mayor of Quezon City after news of Bernardo being dead.
November 8, 1949	Former President Elpidio Quirino is again re-elected as President of the Philippines in the 1949 Philippine Elections. Fernando Lopez is his vice president.
January 6, 1950	Former Quezon City mayor Nicanor Roxas ends his term as mayor. Ignacio Diaz replaces him as the mayor of the capital.
February 1, 1950	The University of Sto. Tomas demonstrated an experimental home-made television receiver, led by engineering student Jose O. Nicolas.
March 1, 1950	Loreto F. de Hemedes, Inc., owned by Robert Stewart, introduces DZBB AM Station. It became the first radio station to use telephones on air, as well as producing political satire.
June 1, 1950	Under the command of the United Nations, Philippine army officials went on to provide combat support to the Korean War.
June 14, 1950	The Bolinao Electronics Corporation was granted license in the Philippine Congress to establish a radio broadcasting station.
October 1, 1950	The HUKBALAHAP and the PKP offensive is being spearheaded by the government, with former defense secretary Ramon Magsaysay leading the charge and President Quirino suspending the writ of habeas corpus for communists.
January 1, 1951	Executive Order No. 392 transferred the Radio Control Board to the Department of Public Works and Communications (DPWC).

August 1, 1951	The origins for the National Movement for Free Elections (NAMFREL) is established, with the introduction of the election operations registration committee.
December 4, 1951	Mt. Hibok-Hibok in Camiguin island is reported to erupt that morning, official accounts of the eruption is said to be covered by DZBB-TV and possibly other radio stations.
1952	The FEATI Institute of Technology (now FEATI University) introduces an experimental television station. Meanwhile, Judge Antonio Quirino buys out 70% of the total shares in the Bolinao Electronics Corporation. Aleli de Guzman Quirino and Antonio Quirino become the owners of BEC, while Lindenberg becomes the co-owner of the company. BEC is then renamed as Alto Broadcasting System (ABS).
October 29, 1952	The National Press Club of the Philippines (NPC) is founded through the initiative of newspaperman Teodoro Valencia.
May 6, 1953	Quirino initiates the importation of 120 television sets through the loan received from Joe's Electric, Joe's Electric then becomes the first to sell television sets in the Philippines.
October 23, 1953	Alto Broadcasting System (ABS) made its first telecast as DZAQ-TV Channel 3, with the first telecast was a party at the owner's residence, which earned former President Elpidio Quirino the honor of being the first Filipino to appear on television.
November 1, 1953	The first stage play in the Philippines is introduced, which is Cyrano de Bergerac, produced by Atenean priest and professor, James Bertram Reuter. This move would then create a generation of stage performers that then would be known as the "Reuter babies".
November 10, 1953	The results for the 1953 Philippine presidential elections made Ramon Magsaysay as the President and Carlos Garcia as the Vice President.
December 30, 1953	Former mayor Ignacio Diaz ends his term as the mayor of Quezon City.
January 11, 1954	The first elected mayor of Quezon City, Norberto S. Amoranto, assumes into the office of the mayor.
February 1, 1954	"Operation Thunder-Lightning" is now done to defeat the rebellion of the HUKBALAHAP group.
May 17, 1954	Luis Taruc, Supremo of the HUKBALAHAP, surrenders to Pres. Magsaysay during "Operation Thunder-Lightning".
July 21, 1954	The Southeast Asia Collective Defense Treaty is signed in Manila, which prompted the creation of the South East Asian Treaty Organization (SEATO).
September 1, 1954	"Operation Thunder-Lightning" ceases its operation with the HUKBALAHAP being dismantled from the inside. The South East Asian Treaty Organization (SEATO) is now established in Manila.
1955	Radiowealth Inc. of Domingo Guevara becomes the first to manufacture locally made television sets with wooden cabinetry, he first advertised them under the name, Radiowealth-Motorola. Carlsound and Rehco would then follow Radiowealth as local television manufacturers.

April 1, 1955	Chronicle Broadcasting Network (CBN) was created by Eugenio and Fernando Lopez, owners of the Manila Chronicle.
November 1, 1955	The start of the Vietnam War.
May 9, 1965	Chronicle Broadcasting Network (CBN) now operates as a broadcasting medium, the Lopezes would then acquire the Alto Broadcasting System (ABS) under a contract written over breakfast.
June 15, 1956	Republic Act No. 1476 abolished the Radio Control Board, with the Radio Control Division remaining under the DPWC.
June 18, 1956	Alpheus Williams, one of the people behind the Quezon City plan made by Frost and Arellano, died in his hometown in Culpeper, Virginia.
February 19, 1957	The Public Relations Society of the Philippines (PRSP) is founded.
February 24, 1957	Alto Broadcasting System (ABS) is formally acquired by the Lopezes, prompting the start of ABS-CBN. ABS-CBN is a merger of the DZAQ-TV Channel 3 and DZXL-TV Channel 9.
March 17, 1957	Former President Ramon Magsaysay dies when his plane crashed on Mount Manunggal in Balamban, Cebu. Only veteran journalist Nestor Mata survived the plane crash with lots of injuries.
March 18, 1957	Former vice president Carlos Garcia takes over as the President of the Philippines, after returning home from an official delegation in SEATO in Canberra, Australia.
March 22, 1957	At least two million people is reported to have attended the state funeral of former President Ramon Magsaysay, which is covered by different media outlets, including a known coverage of DZBB-TV.
November 12, 1957	The 1957 Philippine presidential elections ended up with President Carlos Garcia to be re-elected and Diosdado Macapagal to be elected as the vice president.
June 13, 1958	The National Science Development Board was established, it was predecessor to the Department of Science and Technology (DOST).
May 12, 1960	DZBB-TV changes its headquarters in EDSA, Diliman, Quezon City.
November 10, 1959	Former mayor Norberto S. Amoranto wins again in the elections of being the mayor of Quezon City.
June 19, 1960	Republic Act No. 2717, or the Electrification Administration Act, is enacted. This becomes the start of a industrializing electric power in the Philippines.
December 5, 1960	Juan Arellano, one of the architects of the Master Plan of Quezon City, died at the age of 72.
1961	The National Science Development Board did the earliest initiatives to use local television for education, such as "Education on TV" and "Physics in the Atomic Age."
April 18, 1961	BayanTel was incorporated as the operating arm of BTHC and formerly known as International Communications Corporation (ICC).
October 29, 1961	RBS TV Channel 7 was launched by the Loreto F. de Hemedes, Inc. and made it as the Republic Broadcasting System, Inc.
November 7, 1961	Former Vice President Diosdado Macapagal is elected as the President of the Philippines.
May 15, 1965	Capitol Wireless Inc (Capwire) is established.

May 12, 1962	Former President Diosdado Macapagal changes the date of Independence in the Philippines to June 12, while July 4 became known as the Philippine-American friendship day.
August 23, 1962	Department Order No. 51 changed the name of the Radio Control Division to Radio Control Office.
June 7-11, 1963	The Manila Accord is attended by former President Macapagal, Sukarno, and Abdul Rahman, creating the idea for the Maphilindo confederation.
July 28, 1963	The Philippine contingent, consisting of 24 boy scouts, died in a plane crash in the Indian Ocean.
July 31, 1963	The Maphilindo confederation is signed by the three leaders that attended the Manila Accord.
August 10, 1963	A republic act is passed providing for the regulation of radio stations and radio communications in the country.
August 14, 1964	The 1964 Miss International is won by Gemma Cruz.
November 30, 1964	Jose Maria Sison establishes the Kabataang Makabayan along with Nilo Tayag as an extension of the Student Cultural Association of the University of the Philippines (SCAUP).
June 19, 1965	Globe Wireless Limited was merged with Mackay Radio & Telegraph Company and Philippine Press Wireless to form Globe-Mackay Cable and Radio Corporation ("Globe-Mackay") approved by the Congress through Republic Act No. 4491.
November 9, 1965	Former President Diosdado Macapagal is replaced by Ferdinand Marcos Sr. as the President of the Philippines.
July 1, 1966	Former President Ferdinand Marcos signs the Vietnam Aid Law.
August 1, 1966	The Philippine Congress approves the Philippine Civil Action Group (PHILCAG) to be sent to South Vietnam to aid to the Vietnam War.
September 1, 1966	The first batch of the Philippine Civil Action Group (PHILCAG) goes to South Vietnam.
October 1, 1966	Former President Ferdinand Marcos hosts the Manila Summit.
March 1, 1967	General Telephone and Electric (GTE) disposed of their 28% controlling interest in PLDT.
August 8, 1967	The Association of Southeast Asian Nation (ASEAN) is formed in Bangkok, Thailand.
November 7, 1967	Philippines Telecommunications Investment Corporation (PTIC) was registered to buy GTE's controlling interest. Ramon Cojuangco was a main incorporator.
December 20, 1967	Filipino entrepreneurs and businessmen led by Ramon Cojuangco took control of PLDT after buying its shares from General Telephone and Electronics Corporation.
January 1, 1968	Cojuangco group took control of PLDT's management, becoming a dominant player in telecommunications because of its authorization to operate a national network.
September 1, 1968	Former President Ferdinand Marcos Sr. defining country's territorial waters and claims Sabah as part of the country's territory.
December 26, 1968	The Communist Party of the Philippines is reestablished by Jose Maria Sison in Pangasinan.

March 29, 1968	The New People's Army is organized as the military part of the Communist Party of the Philippines.
May 21, 1969	The Senate pointed out that only 22.9% of all the homes had electricity. 62.8% of the total number of homes were in the cities and only 5.8% of homes were electrified.
July 19, 1969	The 1969 Miss Universe is won by Gloria Diaz.
July 28, 1969	Republic Act No. 6038, or the National Electrification Administration Act, is approved.
August 4, 1969	The National Electrification Administration (NEA) was created by virtue of Republic Act 6038 that declared a national policy objective of the total electrification of the Philippines.
November 11, 1969	Former President Ferdinand Marcos Sr. is then re-elected as the President of the Philippines.
May 23, 1969	PLDT was nationalized by the government of former President Ferdinand Marcos
January 26, 1970	The First Quarter Storm is initiated during the State of the Nation Address of Former President Ferdinand Marcos Sr. in the Legislative Building (now the National Museum of Fine Arts) in Manila.
March 3, 1970	The People's March during the First Quarter Storm started at Welcome Rotonda in Quezon City.
April 1, 1970	Other rallies have started, protesting fare costs and oil prices.
June 27, 1970	Former President Marcos endorses the Barrio Self-Defense Units, which is later called the Civilian Home Defense Units.
February 1, 1971	The start of the Diliman Commune, renaming the University of the Philippines as the Malayang Komunidad ng UP Diliman.
February 9, 1971	The Diliman Commune ends.
October 1, 1978	Louis Croft, part of the Frost plan, died in Bethesda, Maryland.
June 1, 1971	The Constitutional Convention assembles to rewrite the 1935 Constitution, with the head being former President Carlos Garcia.
June 14, 1971	Former President Carlos Garcia dies.
August 21, 1971	Plaza Miranda bombing
August 22, 1971	Due to the Plaza Miranda, the writ of habeas corpus is suspended again by former President Ferdinand Marcos Sr.
June 27, 1970	Former President Marcos endorses the Barrio Self-Defense Units, which is later called the Civilian Home Defense Units.
November 27, 1970	Pope Paul VI makes his first papal visit in the country and survived an assassination attempt by a Bolivian painter named Benjamin Mendoza.
December 29, 1970	Lieutenant Victor Corpuz raids the armory of the Philippine Military Academy and defects to the New People's Army.
September 1, 1971	Termination of operations in the US Sangley Point Naval Base.

November 1, 1971	The 1971 Philippine Senate elections.
1972	The Constitutional Convention approves the parliamentary form of government. The Board of Commissions authorized Capwire to provide international records communication services, particularly telegraph and leased circuits.
January 1, 1972	Former President Ferdinand Marcos Sr. restores the writ of habeas corpus in the Philippines.
May 9, 1972	Propaganda newspaper outlet "Philippine Daily Express" is founded by Roberto Benedicto.
June 1, 1972	Formal establishment of the "Philippine Daily Express".
September 13, 1972	Former Senator Benigno "Ninoy" Aquino Jr. exposes a secret agenda of seizing the Capital, named as Oplan Saggitarius.
September 21, 1972	Former President Marcos announces Martial Law to be imposed nationwide, although this has not been announced yet.
September 22, 1972	Former Minister of Defense Juan Ponce Enrile survives a staged assassination at the Wack Wack Country and Golf Club in Mandaluyong. Former President Marcos announces Martial Law in the Philippines, ordering all media outlets except for those that are exempted, to be closed.
September 23, 1972	Martial Law in the Philippines is officially announced., all media outlets are shut down or minimized in their broadcasting power by the government, except for those that are owned by Marcos crony Roberto Benedicto.
September 24, 1972	Integrated Reorganization Plan (IRP), retained the Radio Control Office with functions relative to the enforcement of policies, rules and regulations on telecommunications.
September 26, 1972	The Philippines is proclaimed as a land reform area and an Agrarian Reform Program is decreed by former President Marcos.
October 1, 1972	Presidential Decree No. 27 is issued, with states the land reform program.
November 29, 1972	The 1973 Constitution of the Philippines is passed on by the Constitutional Convention.
December 7, 1972	Presidential First Lady Imelda Marcos survives an assassination attempt by Carlito Dimahilig.
1973	Former President Marcos Sr. mandated all PLDT subscribers to invest in PLDT to raise its equity and finance its expansion program. This law, known as the Subscribers Investment Plan (SIP) required all PLDT subscribers to buy non-voting shares in the company.
January 10-15, 1973	The 1973 Philippine Constitutional Plebiscite is held to ratify the 1972 Constitution.
January 17, 1973	Former President Marcos Sr. declares the 1973 Constitution, and orders that the Congress of the Philippines to be padlocked.
March 1, 1973	Philippine News Agency is formally established.
March 31, 1973	The Supreme Court of the Philippines upholds the validity of the 1973 Philippine Constitution.
April 1, 1973	The National Democratic Front (NDF), Communist Party of the Philippines' united front, is formally established.

May 1, 1973	The Masagana 99 Program is launched.
July 21, 1973	The 1973 Miss Universe declares Margarita Moran as the winner of the pageant.
July 27, 1973	Former President Marcos Sr. extended term as the President of the Philippines under a false referendum.
1974	Ayala Corporation began its investing in Globe-Mackay.
February 27, 1974	Presidential appointments of Former President Marcos Sr. to local elective positions is declared legal by virtue of a referendum.
March 11, 1974	Japanese Lt. Hiroo Onoda formally surrenders in a ceremony held in Malacañang.
June 24, 1974	Former President Marcos Sr. authorized the transfer of Eastern Extension's franchise to a newly established firm Eastern Telecommunications Philippines (ETPI), co-owned by Universal Molasses Corporation (UNIMOLCO).
July 1, 1974	Integrated Reorganization Plan (IRP) is renamed as the Telecommunications Control Bureau.
July 1, 1974	The Parity Rights Amendment of the Laurel-Langley Trade Act expires.
July 21, 1974	The 1974 Miss Universe pageant is held in the Folk Arts Theater of the Cultural Center of the Philippines.
September 1, 1974	Jose Diokno is ordered by Former Pres. Marcos Sr. to be released.
September 17, 1974	The Supreme Court of the Philippines upholds the declaration of martial law and dismisses petitions in regard to the writ of habeas corpus.
September 21, 1974	By virtue of Presidential Decree No. 527, September 21 is declared Barangay Day, and Barangays are now reorganized.
December 24, 1974	A wiretap by the US Embassy in Manila reveals the existence of Rolex 12, a group of people that is heavily associated with the dictatorship of former President Ferdinand Marcos Sr.
May 28, 1905	Around 60 small telephone companies provided 11.7% of the total telephone capacity
February 1, 1975	Former press censor and propagandist Primitivo Mijares defects from the government of former President Marcos.
February 27-28, 1975	The third national referendum during the administration of former President Marcos Sr. allows the continuation of the former President to be the head of state.
April 4, 1975	Former Senator Ninoy Aquino starts out his 40-day hunger strike as a form of protest to the government of former President Marcos Sr.
April 9, 1975	The Philippine Basketball Association is founded.
June 1, 1975	Defector Primitivo Mijares presents himself to the US Congress to testify against the corruption of the Marcoses back in the Philippines.
August 11, 1975	Globe-Mackay offered its shares to the public.
October 2, 1975	The Thrilla in Manila happened at the Araneta Coliseum, where Muhammad Ali won against his opponent Joe Frazier. This event eventually made the

	district of Cubao be popular, especially near the area in the Araneta Coliseum, where Alimall will then be established soon after.
May 29, 1905	The Philippine Association of Private Telephone Companies was organized to protect the interest of small telephone companies.
October 16-17, 1976	Martial Law in the Philippines is extended by the virtue of the national referendum plebiscite in 1976.
December 23, 1976	The Tripoli Agreement is signed between the Philippine government and the Moro National Liberation Front.
1977	Philippine Global Communications (Philcom) is established. During the term of former President Marcos Sr., he gave Philcom exclusive rights to handle calls to Japan, Australia, Korea, Guam, and Thailand.
January 20, 1977	The Armed Forces of the Philippines enters a ceasefire agreement to the Moro National Liberation Front.
March 4, 1977	Former President Marcos Sr. issues a decree creating the autonomous Bangsamoro Islamic Government
August 1, 1977	Former President Marcos Sr. announces amnesty for persons found guilty of subversion against the Philippine government.
August 22, 1977	Curfew hours are lifted by the government.
October 1, 1977	Eugenio Lopez Jr. of ABS-CBN Channel 2 and Sergio Osmeña III escaped from detention in Fort Bonifacio and flee to the United States to testify against the Philippine government.
November 10, 1977	Leader of the Communist Party of the Philippines, Jose Maria Sison, is arrested, along with members of the Communist Party of the Philippines.
November 25, 1977	The military court finds former Senator Ninoy Aquino, Bernabe Buscayno of the New People's Army and military defector Victor Corpuz guilty of their charges and sentences them to death by firing squad, but the sentence has never been imposed.
December 16, 1977	Another national referendum empowers former President Marcos Sr. to continue in office, and to become Prime Minister of the Philippines.
1978	Capwire became the second largest domestic telegraph carrier in the country after acquiring domestic telegraph carriers to expand its nationwide network.
April 7, 1978	The member of the Interim Batasang Pambansa is elected, headed by former President Ferdinand Marcos Sr.
June 1, 1978	Inauguration of the Interim Batasang Pambansa.
January 1, 1979	Amendment of the US military Base Forces
April 10, 1979	Former President Marcos Sr. issues Presidential Decree No. 1616 creating the Intramuros Administration, tasked to recreate the walled city of Intramuros.
July 23, 1979	Executive Order No. 546 abolished the Telecommunications Control Bureau and the Board of Communications, integrating it into a single entity, the National Telecommunications Commission (NTC).
July 30, 1979	Noontime show "Eat Bulaga!" premiered on RPN Channel 9.

October 30, 1979	Project Gintong Alay, dedicated for enhancing the sports program in the Philippines, is commenced.
November 1, 1979	The Bataan Nuclear Power Plant (BNPP) ceases construction.
December 1, 1979	Former Senator Ninoy Aquino is released from detention.
June 2, 1905	Local elections in the Philippines are held amidst massive boycotts.
May 1, 1980	Kilusang Mayo Uno is founded.
May 1, 1980	Former President Marcos Sr. allows former Senator Ninoy Aquino to go to the United States for medical treatment.
December 24, 1980	Globe-Mackay was granted a new franchise by Batasang Pambansa, under Batas Pambansa Blg. 95.
1981	PLDT purchased substantially all of the assets and liabilities of Republic Telephone Company, becoming a monopoly. Former President Marcos Sr. issued a presidential directive to Retelco, PLDT's main competitor in Metro Manila, to merge with PLDT. The merger was met with objection by the owners of Retelco, but the merger was continued because Marcos threatened to withdraw the companies' franchises.
January 17, 1981	By virtue of Proclamation No. 2045, the Martial Law in the Philippines is lifted by former President Marcos Sr.
February 17-21, 1981	Pope John Paul II visited the Philippines for his first papal visit.
April 7, 1981	Executive Committee is created by a constitutional amendment which is ratified in a national plebiscite.
June 16, 1981	Former President Marcos Sr. is re-elected again for the third time in the 1981 Philippine Presidential Elections.
June 30, 1981	Former President Marcos Sr. is inaugurated again as the President of the Philippines while Cesar Virata is now the Prime Minister of the Interim Batasang Pambansa.
November 17, 1981	The Manila Film Center accident in Pasay, where 169 construction workers were killed.
January 18-29, 1982	The International Film Festival is held at the Manila Film Center.
April 1, 1982	The United Nationalist Democratic Opposition is formed.
May 1, 1982	The Barangay elections are held for the first time.
July 23, 1982	The Reform the Armed Forces Movement is formed.
December 1, 1982	We Forum and Malaya shut down by former President Marcos Sr. for engaging in "black propaganda."
August 21, 1983	Former Senator Ninoy Aquino is assassinated at the Manila International Airport.

August 31, 1983	About seven million people attended the funeral of former Senator Ninoy Aquino, which then turned into a rally.
November 21, 1983	The Good Shepherd Sisters died in the sinking of the M/V Doña Cassandra off the coast of Surigao
January 27, 1984	Executive Committee is abolished and the Office of the Vice President is restored through a constitutional amendment.
May 14, 1984	The 1984 Philippine parliamentary election is held.
June 1, 1984	The National Assembly assembles and reconfirms Prime Minister Virata and Nicanor Yniguez is elected as the Speaker.
August 19, 1984	El Shaddai led by Bro. Mike Z. Velarde, is established.
December 1, 1984	LRT Line 1 is opened.
July 1, 1985	Former President Marcos Sr. transfers the control of the Integrated National Police to his control.
August 1, 1985	Opposition Parliament members file impeachment charges against Former President Marcos Sr.
November 3, 1985	Former President Marcos Sr. announces a snap election.
December 2, 1985	Sandiganbayan frees charges of AFP Chief of Staff Gen. Fabian Ver and 26 others accused in the assassination of Ninoy Aquino.
February 7, 1986	The 1986 Philippine presidential election is held.
February 9, 1986	Linda Kapunan-Hill and 34 other COMELEC computer workers walked out at PICC due to cheating allegations in the elections.
February 16, 1986	Cory Aquino, is proclaimed President in Luneta and calls for a civil disobedience campaign as a protest.
February 22-25, 1986	EDSA People Power Revolution ousts former President Marcos Sr.
February 22, 1986	Defense Minister Juan Ponce Enrile and Constabulary Chief Gen. Fidel Ramos withdraw from the Marcos administration. Crowds gather at Camp Crame and Aguinaldo in Cubao, Cardinal Sin urges the public to join in a peaceful revolt.
February 23, 1986	Crowds gather to Ortigas Avenue and EDSA to stop the targeting Marine forces and support the presidency of Cory Aquino.
February 24, 1986	Air Force joins in the reformists in supporting the presidency of Cory Aquino, attacks are introduced in Villamor Airbase, Camp Aguinaldo, and the Malacañang. The Manila Broadcasting System Channel 4 is shut down temporarily.
February 25, 1986	Cory Aquino is sworn in as president and Salvador "Doy" Laurel as vice president at Club Filipino in San Juan. Aquino appoints Enrile as Defense Secretary and Ramos as AFP Chief of Staff. Former President Marcos also inaugurates himself but is transported to Clark Air Base in Pampanga.
February 26, 1986	The Marcos family leaves for Guam and Hawaii aboard American planes.

February 28, 1986	The Presidential Commission on Good Government (PCGG) is created by former President Aquino.
March 5, 1986	Former President Aquino frees political prisoners Jose Maria Sison of the Communist Party of the Philippines and Bernabe Buscayno of the New People's Army.
March 25, 1986	A revolutionary government is established by former President Aquino, which also abolishes Interim Batasang Pambansa and the 1973 Constitution and adopts Freedom Constitution by the virtue of Proclamation No. 3.
July 6-8, 1986	A coup is staged by Arturo Tolentino along with Marcos loyalists in the Manila Hotel and several thousand supporters.
July 22, 1986	ABS-CBN is back in the airwaves. DZMM AM becomes the first post-revolution AM station, while DWKO FM becomes the first post-revolution FM station.
1986	Establishment of first BBS in the Philippines, First-Fil RBBS by Dan Angeles and Ed Castañeda. Antonio "Tonyboy" O. Cojuangco, Jr. became chief executive of PLDT.
November 6, 1986	Labor leaders Rolando Olalia and Leonor Alay-ay by members of the Reform the Armed Forces Movement, this was thought to be a part of the "God Save The Queen" plan.
November 11, 1986	The scheduled part for the "God Save The Queen" coup plan organized by Defense Secretary Enrile and the Reform the Armed Forces Movement (RAM).
1987	The Philippine FidoNet Exchange, a local network for communication between several BBSes in Metro Manila, was formed. The DOTC adopted a series of policies aimed at rationalizing the development of the industry. This led to the reversal of Marcos' push towards the integration of the telecommunications system under a monopoly.
January 22, 1987	Thirteen farmers died in Mendiola during a rally that is caused by the police and the military, which is known as the Mendiola Massacre.
January 27-29, 1987	Col. Oscar Canlas and other rebel soldiers seize the GMA Network compound in EDSA and military bases in Pasay and in Sangley Point in Cavite, causing one death and 16 accounted injuries.
February 2, 1987	The Constitutional Commission drafts the 1987 Constitution, and is ratified in a plebiscite.
February 11, 1987	The 1987 Constitution is declared ratified, replacing the Freedom Constitution or Proclamation No. 3.
March 2, 1987	TV Patrol first aired on ABS-CBN.
April 18, 1987	56 rebel soldiers staged a raid in Fort Bonifacio, leading to one death.
May 11, 1987	The 1987 Philippine legislative election is held, being the first free elections held in almost two decades and under the 1987 Constitution.
July 1, 1987	A plot to take over the Manila International Airport is discovered, with four soldiers being court-martialled for their actions.
March 20, 1987	Agila-1 or Mabuhay was launched under the name Palapa B2-P in Cape Canaveral Air Force Station

August 28–29, 1987	The August coup attempt led by colonel Gringo Honasan, with many assaults including Malacañang Palace, Camp Aguinaldo, Villamor Air Base, various television stations, and military camps in Pampanga and Cebu resulting in 53 fatalities and over 200 injuries.
1988	Extelcom, through the granting of a purchasing agent, operates as an analogue cellular service provider in Metro Manila and selected urban centers in the provinces via BayanTel.
January 18, 1988	Local elections are held under the new 1987 Constitution.
April 2, 1988	Col. Gringo Honasan escapes in his refuge in a navy ship in Manila Bay.
June 10, 1988	Former President Aquino signs the Comprehensive Agrarian Reform Program (CARP) into law.
October 1, 1988	The Marcos couple have been charged in the United States for illegal money transfer during their time in the Philippines.
October 17, 1988	The 1988 Interior Bases Agreement was signed by the Philippines and United States.
June 11, 1985	The company was granted permission to provide alternative voice and data services, enabling it to branch out into the international voice service arena.
April 21, 1989	Col. James Rowe is assassinated by the Communists, which prompts the issue of removal of the U.S. military bases from the country.
August 1, 1989	Former President Aquino signs Republic Act No. 6734, a law creating the Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (ARMM).
September 28, 1989	Former President Ferdinand Marcos Sr. dies while in exile.
November 19, 1989	A plebiscite is done for the creation of the Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (ARMM).
December 1-9, 1989	Col. Honasan and Marcos loyalists under retired Gen. Jose Ma. Zúñiga bombards the Malacañang Palace, resulting in 99 deaths.
December 21, 1989	Republic Act No. 6849, known as the Municipal Telephone Act of 1989 is passed.
1990	Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (ARMM) is officially created. Arnie del Rosario of the Ateneo Computer Technology Center was tasked with exploring the possibility of creating an academic network of universities and government institutions by the National Computer Center under Dr. William Torres. Recommendations were made but not implemented.
February 8, 1990	The Municipal Telephone Act of 1989 is approved.
June 1, 1990	American Peace Corps removed 261 volunteers from the country amid Communist threats.
June 6, 1990	Sky Cable Corporation was incorporated as Central CATV, Inc.
July 16, 1990	The 1990 Luzon earthquake affected Northern and Central Luzon.
September 1, 1990	16 military members are convicted and sentenced to life imprisonment regarding the killing of former Senator Ninoy Aquino.

June 13, 1905	Globe-Mackay merged with Clavecilla Radio Corporation, a domestic telecommunications pioneer, to form GMCR, Inc. PLDT had 94% of all the local telephone lines. DOTC and Capwire entered into a joint venture deal for the installation and operation of a nationwide VSAT network known as the Philippine Satellite Communication Network or Philsat.
January 24, 1991	A group of Filipino investors led by Orlando B. Veja and David T. Fernando organized Smart Information Technology, Inc.
January 29, 1991	The Philippine National Police is formed with the merger of the Philippine Constabulary with the Integrated National Police.
March 25, 1991	Sky Vision Corporation, a holding company incorporated with the primary purpose of buying and owning stocks of Central CATV, Inc. was founded.
June 12-15, 1991	The 1991 Eruption of Mt. Pinatubo, which affected Central Luzon.
November 1, 1991	Former First Lady Imelda Marcos returns to the Philippines to face charges against her.
1992	PLDT partnered with AT&T Corporation to expand its services into rural communities. PCGG and Marcos Sr. crony Roberto Benedicto signed a compromise agreement wherein Benedicto surrendered 51% of his equity stake in ETPI.
January 1, 1992	Former First Lady Imelda Marcos is arrested and later released on charges regarding her accounts in Switzerland.
March 19, 1992	The GMCR, Inc. merger was approved by Congress through Republic Act No. 7229
April 1, 1992	Smart Information Technology, Inc. obtained its congressional franchise.
May 11, 1992	The 1992 Philippine presidential election, which results in the victory of former President Fidel Ramos and former Vice President Joseph Estrada.
August 17, 1992	Hit television show Mara Clara airson ABS-CBN, it will be then called as the "Mother of Pinoy Soap Opera".
1993	Globe partnered with Singapore Telecom, Inc. (STI), a wholly owned subsidiary of Singapore Telecommunications Limited ("Singtel"). Extelcom, through a certificate of public convenience and necessity, expands operations via BayanTel.
May 1, 1993	Smart Information Technology, Inc. is granted with a provisional authority to operate a mobile cellular service
June 1, 1993	With the support of the Department of Science and Technology and the Industrial Research Foundation, the Philnet project (now PHNET) was born.
July 1, 1993	Phase one of the Philnet project shifted into full gear after receiving funding from DOST.
September 1, 1993	The remains of former President Ferdinand Marcos Sr. return in the country upon permission from the government and is interred in his hometown in Batac, Ilocos Norte.
September 24, 1993	Former First Lady Imelda Marcos is found by Sandiganbayan to be guilty of corruption.
November 1, 1993	An additional P12.5-million grant for the first year's running cost was awarded by the DOST to buy equipment and lease communication lines

	needed to kickstart the second phase of Philnet, now led by Dr. Rudy Villarica.
December 1, 1993	Smart commenced commercial operations of its cellular service.
1994	<p>The NTC and several other industry players devised the Service Area Scheme (SAS) This scheme was in response to imbalanced demand of telecom companies in urban areas over rural areas. The SAS attempted to allow companies to earn profits but also ensure that part of those profits would be channeled to serve less profitable areas.</p> <p>Globe launched its digital cellular services, pioneering the use of Global System for Mobile Communications Technology (GSM). Globe also popularized the short messaging service (SMS) through adding it for free with their basic services.</p> <p>Capwire was granted the Provisional Authority to operate International Gateway Facility (IGF) by the NTC and became one of the 11 authorized IGF operators in the country.</p>
March 29, 1994	The Philippines first makes its connection to the Internet, as the Philippine Network Foundation is connected to United States' Sprint via a 64 kbit/s link.
November 10, 1994	Mabuhay Philippine Satellite Corporation (MPSC) is founded.
January 10-15, 1995	Pope Saint John Paul II visits the Philippines and presides over the country's first World Youth Day in Manila.
February 1, 1995	Philippine Navy spots the creation of structures and ships in the territories of the Philippines in the West Philippine Sea, which initiates the Philippines to file a case against China.
March 1, 1995	Public Telecommunications Policy Act of the Philippines is approved. PLDT is de-monopolized.
March 30, 1995	Central CATV Inc. was granted a 25-year provisional franchise through Republic Act 7969.
May 17, 1995	11 members of Kuratong Baleleng were killed by the forces of the Presidential Anti-Crime Commission, led by Police General Panfilo Lacson.
November 27, 1995	The construction of the Skyway project, intended to be the biggest infrastructure project in the country that was intended to ease the flow of traffic in Metro Manila.
1995	<p>BTHC purchased its initial interest in Extelcom for approximately US\$140.0 million.</p> <p>Through its wholly owned subsidiary, Wavenet Philippines, Inc., Capwire ventured into the Internet business.</p>
March 18, 1996	Ozone Disco in Panay Avenue burned down, killing 158, including students.
September 2, 1996	The Jakarta Accord, or the Final Peace Agreement, is signed in Malacañang Palace with the Philippine Government and the Moro National Liberation Front.
1997	<p>BTHC infused PhP765.5 million as part of a capital-raising exercise undertaken by Extelcom.</p> <p>Sky Vision Corporation acquired 47% of Pilipino Cable Corporation for 900 million pesos.</p>

July 1, 1997	The Philippines faced an economic crisis because of the Asian financial crisis.
August 19, 1997	PLDT, through Mabuhay Satellite Corporation, launched the Philippines' first local communications satellite Agila II
October 29, 1997	Former President Fidel Ramos signs Indigenous Peoples' Rights Act (Republic Act No. 8371), with the creation of National Commission on Indigenous Peoples (NCIP).
June 20, 1905	Hong Kong-based First Pacific Company Ltd. acquired a 17.5% controlling stake in PLDT for approximately P29.7 billion. Manuel V. Pangilinan becomes chairman of PLDT.
April 19, 1998	Mindanao Islamic Telephone Company, Inc. (Mislattel), is enacted by Congressional legislation
May 11, 1998	Former Vice President Joseph Estrada becomes the President of the Philippines after the 1998 Philippine presidential elections.
June 12, 1998	Centennial Anniversary of Philippine Independence, with a two-day celebration in the country.
August 20, 1998	GMCR was renamed as Globe Telecom, Inc.
February 5, 1999	Rape convict Leo Echegaray is executed by lethal injection at the New Bilibid Prison in Muntinlupa.
May 1, 1999	The New Visiting Forces Agreement (VFA) with the United States is ratified by the Philippine Senate.
March 24, 2000	PLDT completed its share-swap acquisition of Smart, making Smart a 100%-owned PLDT subsidiary.
May 1, 2000	The ILOVEYOU virus, originating in Manila, spread around the world, with AMA Computer College student Onel de Guzman being the main culprit.
July 10, 2000	The Payatas trash landslide in Quezon City, killing 218 and reported 300 people that were missing.
July 1, 2000	Mayor Ismael Mathay Jr. reopens the Payatas dumpsite weeks later, as to avoid the local epidemic of uncollected trash in the city.
November 13, 2000	Impeachment of former President Joseph Estrada by the House of Representatives on accusations regarding gambling money
December 7, 2000	Initiation of the impeachment trial against former President Joseph Estrada by the Senate.
December 30, 2000	Rizal Day bombings, where a series of bombs exploded in Metro Manila, which included a bomb in Plaza Ferguson in Malate, a gas station in Makati Central Business District, a cargo handling area at the Ninoy Aquino International Airport, a bus in EDSA in Cubao area, and a LRT train cab in Blumentritt station.
January 16-20, 2000	EDSA People Power Revolution 2, ousting former President Joseph Estrada and installing former Vice President Gloria Arroyo as the new President.
January 16, 2000	Prosecutors of the trial walk out after senators voted, 11–10, not to open the second envelope containing the documents of evidences against Pres. Estrada, regarding his supposed link to a bank account purportedly containing kickbacks from an illegal numbers game; crowd start to gather in the People Power Shrine and conduct the mass rallies, calling for his resignation.

January 17, 2000	Impeachment trial of former President Joseph Estrada is aborted.
January 19, 2000	Defense Secretary Orlando Mercado, AFP Chief of Staff Gen. Angelo Reyes and PNP Chief Dir. Gen. Panfilo Lacson, withdraw from the Estrada administration.
January 20, 2000	Former President Joseph Estrada resigns and leaves Malacañang. Vice President Macapagal Arroyo is sworn into at Our Lady of EDSA Shrine in Mandaluyong.
April 1, 2000	Piltel launched its GSM brand, Talk 'N Text.
August 7, 2000	Digitel was granted a permit by the NTC to establish and operate a Nationwide Cellular Mobile Telephone System (CMTS) using Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM) and/or Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA) technology.
2001	Capwire established a state-of-the-art Network Operations Center for the proactive monitoring and maintenance of international and domestic circuits of end-users and partners. Sky Cable and PLDT Home Cable entered into a master consolidation agreement to form the holding company Beyond Cable, Inc.
April 25, 2001	Former President Joseph Estrada, charged with plunder while in office, and his son Jinggoy are arrested following an arrest warrant issued by Sandiganbayan with their co-accused.
April 30 - May 1, 2001	May 1 riots, also known as EDSA III, ending in a violent dispersal and riots, killing four.
June 27, 2001	Globe merged with Isla Communications Company, Inc. (Islacom), a joint venture with Deutsche Telekom as foreign partner. Islacom was also renamed as Innove Communications, Inc.
February 26, 2002	Former President Joseph Estrada admits signing ₱500 million under the name Jose Velarde in Equitable-PCI Bank
October 3, 2002	ETPI was granted a new 25-year legislative franchise under Republic Act No. 9172
December 11, 2002	Through Republic Act No. 9180, DMPI was given the right to establish a permanent franchise to create and manage a wireless telecommunications service.
June 25, 1905	The National Telecommunications Commission (NTC) granted Globe Telecom's application to transfer its fixed line business assets and subscribers to Islacom. Riding on the wave of technology, Capwire began to Voice over Internet Protocol (VoIP) to the market under the brand name iTalkDirect. Vision and Mission Capwire will be a recognized quality provider of customized communication services for carriers and growing businesses.
March 3, 2003	DMPI launched its wireless service, known as Sun Cellular
April 10, 2003	Most of the board of directors agreed to eliminate the word "Philippines" from the Mabuhay Philippine Satellite Corporation (MPSC).
July 27, 2003	The Magdalo Group, led by Army Capt. Gerardo Gambala and LtSG. Antonio Trillanes IV, takes a mutiny at Oakwood Premier apartments in Makati.

2004	Globe invested in G-Xchange, Inc. ("GXI"), a wholly owned subsidiary, to handle the mobile payment and remittance service marketed under the GCash brand using Globe Telecom's network as transport channel.
January 12, 2004	Executive Order No. 269 created the Commission on Information and Communications Technology (CICT), with the NTC as an attached agency.
May 10, 2004	The 2004 Philippine presidential election continues the term of former President Gloria Arroyo.
October 16, 2004	GXI started commercial operations.
November 1, 2004	Globe and seven other leading Asia-Pacific mobile operators ("JV Partners") signed an agreement ("JV agreement") to form the Bridge Alliance.
2005	Former Trade Minister Roberto Ongpin of ISM Communications Corporation (now DITO telecommunications), acquires 57% stake in ETPI. Innove was awarded by the NTC with a nationwide franchise for its fixed line business, allowing it to operate a Local Exchange Carrier service nationwide and expand its network coverage. Smart became the largest cellular operator in the Philippines with over 15.4 million subscribers.
June 6, 2005	Hello Garci scandal of then-President Gloria Arroyo.
August 16, 2005	Executive Order No. 454 transferred the NTC back to the Department of Transportation and Communications (DOTC).
September 6, 2005	Congress rejects the impeachment case of then-President Arroyo.
November 1, 2005	Reformed Value Added Tax Act (also called Expanded VAT) is implemented, as a solution to the government's fiscal crisis.
December 1, 2005	NTC approved Globe Telecom's application for third generation radio frequency spectra to support the upgrade of its cellular mobile telephone system ("CMTS") network to be able to provide 3G services. Globe was assigned with 10-Megahertz (MHz) of the 3G radio frequency spectrum.
February 24, 2006	The entire country is placed under a state of calamity in response to coup rumors.
March 1, 2007	The Permanent Peoples' Tribunal in The Hague finds the Arroyo administration responsible for unsolved killings and disappearances in the country.
April 20, 2007	A contract is signed by the Philippine and Chinese governments for a proposed National Broadband Network, which later found to be corrupted.
August 6, 2007	Former President Macapagal-Arroyo issued Executive Order 648 transferring the NTC back to the CICT.
August 28, 2007	CPP-NPA-NDF leader Jose Maria Sison is arrested at Utrecht, Netherlands.
September 12, 2007	Sandiganbayan and the Office of the Ombudsman convicts former President Joseph Estrada for plunder and sentences him to reclusion perpetua, but acquits him and his co-accused on other charges.
October 1, 2007	Former Trade Minister Ongpin spent P100 million to acquire Smart's stake in ETPI, raising to 67.5%.
October 26, 2007	Former President Joseph Estrada is pardoned and freed from jail after his trial.

November 29, 2007	Senator Antonio Trillanes IV, Brigadier General Danilo Lim, and 25 other Magdalo officers walked out of their trial and marched through the streets of Makati, calling for the ousting of President Gloria Macapagal Arroyo, and seized the Manila Peninsula Hotel along Ayala Avenue. Former Vice-President Teofisto Guingona, Jr. as well as some of the soldiers from the Armed Forces of the Philippines joined the march to the hotel.
2008	Former Trade Minister Ongpin fully acquires ETPI. PLDT introduced its digital subscriber line (DSL) service.
February 8, 2008	Jun Lozada testifies before the Philippine Senate in connection with the National Broadband Network contract deal.
March 6, 2008	Several Congress members call for an investigation into a joint oil exploration agreement in 2004 between the Philippines, China, and Vietnam over Spratly Islands, claiming it unconstitutional.
March 11, 2008	Former First Lady Imelda Marcos is acquitted by a Manila trial court of 32 counts of illegal money transfers.
March 17, 2008	The United States Supreme Court hears oral arguments on a certiorari petition filed by the government, invoking sovereign immunity regarding the enforcement against former Pres. Marcos' estate.
April 1, 2008	BS-CBN Broadcasting Corporation (now ABS-CBN Corporation), started consolidating Sky Cable's fiscal result into its financial statement.
May 19, 2008	Following the approval of the NTC, the subscribers contracts of Touch Mobile (TM) prepaid service were transferred from Innove to Globe, which now operates all wireless prepaid services using its integrated cellular networks.
August 1, 2008	Globe acquired 100% ownership of Entertainment Gateway Group (EGG).
October 30, 2008	Globe, the Bank of the Philippine Islands and Ayala Corporation signed a memorandum of agreement to form a joint venture that would allow rural and low-income customers' access to financial products and services.
November 25, 2008	Globe formed GTI Business Holdings, Inc. (GTIBH) primarily to act as an investment company.
December 1, 2008	CARPER (CARP Extension with Reforms) Act is passed, reforming CARP and extending it until 2014.
March 1, 2009	Philippine Archipelagic Baselines Act (Republic Act 9522) is signed into law by Pres. Macapagal Arroyo, ensuring international recognition of the country's territorial boundaries.
August 8, 2009	Congress granted Converge ICT's (then known as ComClark Network and Technology Corp.) franchise application to construct, install, establish, operate and maintain a telecommunication system throughout the country.
September 26, 2009	Typhoon Ketsana (Ondoy) is the most devastating typhoon to hit the country since Typhoon Patsy (Yoling).
October 1, 2009	The Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP) approved the sale and transfer by BPI of its shares of stock in Pilipinas Savings Bank, Inc. (PSBI), formalizing the creation of the venture. PSBI is now called BPI Globe BankKO, Inc.
October 2, 2009	Typhoon Parma (Pepeng) hits the country.
November 6, 2009	MSC's communication satellite operation business was sold to Asia Broadcast Satellite (ABS)

November 23, 2009	Maguindanao massacre: Fifty-eight people being part of a convoy, including clan members and 32 journalists, are killed and buried in a mass grave in Ampatuan town by an estimated 100 gunmen belonging to a victims' political rival
December 4, 2009	Pres. Macapagal Arroyo places Maguindanao under a state of martial law in connection with the murder incident
December 12, 2009	Pres. Macapagal Arroyo lifts the state of martial law in Maguindanao.
May 10, 2010	The 2010 Philippine presidential elections is the first national computerized election in the Philippine history, took place. (Sentaor Benigno Aquino III is elected as the new president)
August 23, 2010	The Manila Hostage crisis by hostage-taker Rolando Mendoza, killing eight hostages and causing the relationship of Philippines and Hong Kong to sour for a while.
November 18, 2010	Electoral sabotage charges are filed by the Commission on Elections against former Pres. Macapagal Arroyo, arrested on the same day, and the co-accused at the Pasay Regional Trial Court in connection to allegations of electoral fraud.
2011	PLDT acquired Digitel, including Sun Cellular, from JG Summit Holdings.
January 15, 2011	San Miguel Corporation subsidiary Vega Telecom bought 40% stake in ETPI.
February 1, 2011	Smart unveiled the Netphone, its own line of Android-compliant smartphones designed for emerging markets at the GSMA Mobile World Congress in Barcelona, Spain. The Netphone was introduced as the world's first smartphone backed by an operator-managed platform.
March 1, 2011	PLDT acquired 51.55% of the shares of Digital Telecommunications Philippines (Sun Telecommunications) from JG Summit Holdings.
May 1, 2011	Singapore-based firm ST Telemedia acquired 40% of Sky Cable through Philippine Depositary Receipts (PDR) worth 3.612 billion and 250 million pesos of convertible notes to fund the expansion of Sky Cable's broadband internet and cable television services.
June 23, 2011	Former President Aquino III issued Executive Order No. 47 which retains the NTC under the Office of the President as part of the Other Executive Offices (OEO).
October 21, 2011	San Miguel Corporation later bought the remaining stake thru another subsidiary (San Miguel Equity Securities) after ISM divested its own in ETPI.
October 26, 2011	PLDT's subsidiary Smart Communications surrendered the mobile frequency and spectrum being used by its service Red Mobile to the government
2012	The GCash app was launched as a move to transition from cash-in and cash-out outlets to a fully cashless system.
January 13, 2012	The Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) approved the amendment on its articles of incorporation, Mabuhay Satellite Corporation was renamed Mabuhay Investment Corporation.
March 1, 2012	Globe launched Kickstart Ventures, Inc. (Kickstart) to help, support and develop the dynamic and growing community of technopreneurs in the Philippines.

April 1, 2012	An attempt of the Philippine Navy to detain Chinese fishermen caught on the Scarborough Shoal is blocked by China, escalating a diplomatic standoff over the area.
May 11, 2012	Sky Cable acquired the assets of Destiny Cable (from Destiny Cable Inc.), UniCable (from Uni-Cable TV, Inc.) and MyDestiny broadband internet (from Solid Broadband Corporation) with consolidating value of 3.497 billion pesos.
May 29, 2012	Senators vote to convict Chief Justice Renato Corona guilty in the second article of the impeachment case regarding alleged undisclosed wealth, removing him from office.
August 25, 2012	Smart launched the Philippines' first 4G mobile broadband commercial service running on LTE technology.
September 1, 2012	Cybercrime Prevention Act (Republic Act 10175) is signed into law by former President Benigno Aquino III.
December 21, 2012	Reproductive Health Bill is signed into law by former President Benigno Aquino III.
2013	Sky Cable revenues increased by 18% to P6.99 billion from P5.94 billion. Sky discontinued its VOIP service and started offering bundled plans with ABS-CBN mobile postpaid service which includes a wireless landline connection, SMS, and voice.
May 1, 2013	ABS-CBN Convergence, Inc. ("ABS-C", formerly Multimedia Telephony, Inc.) announced the launch of its mobile brand, ABS-CBN mobile.
May 15, 2013	The Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, commonly known as K-12 program was signed.
May 28, 2013	ABS-CBN and wireless telecommunications giant Globe Telecom signed a historic network-sharing agreement which allows the two companies to share assets such as frequencies, switches, servers, and transmitters.
October 1, 2013	Globe acquired a 38% interest in BayanTel by converting BayanTel's unsustainable debt into common shares.
October 15, 2013	A magnitude 7.2 earthquake strikes Bohol province, the country's deadliest earthquake since 1990.
November 8, 2013	Super Typhoon Haiyan (Yolanda) landfalls in Visayas and devastates the country.
November 16, 2013	During the "Tulong Na, Tabang Na, Tayo Na" benefit concert of ABS-CBN for the Typhoon Haiyan victims at the Smart Araneta Coliseum, the service was officially launched to the public.
November 18, 2013	A television advertisement of ABS-CBN mobile featuring Kim Chiu, Piolo Pascual, Enrique Gil and John Lloyd Cruz was officially previewed.
November 26, 2013	ABS-C formally launched ABS-CBN mobile.
December 11, 2013	The first ABS-CBN mobile store and service center opened at the ground floor level of ELJ Communications Center.
May 15, 2014	EGGC changed its corporate name from Entertainment Gateway Group Corp. to Yondu, Inc. (Yondu).
June 3, 2014	Globe signed an agreement with Azalea Technology, Inc. and SCS Computer Systems, acquiring the entire ownership stake in Asticom.
July 27, 2014	Philippines marks a milestone in its population growth identifying the birth of a baby girl in a Manila hospital as the 100 millionth Filipino.

September 10, 2014	Former President Benigno Aquino III leads the handover of the draft of the Bangsamoro Basic Law in a historical turnover ceremony at the Malacañang.
October 1, 2014	Globe Telecom received a copy of the temporary restraining order (TRO) issued by the Court of Appeals stopping the NTC proceedings in connection with the bid to take over Bayan Telecommunications Inc. (BayanTel).
December 9, 2014	The Court of Appeals has advised the NTC to refrain from conducting any proceedings in connection with the bid of Globe assume majority control of BayanTel.
January 15–19, 2015	Papal visit of Pope Francis in the Philippines, with a special Mass held at the Tacloban airport on the 17th.
January 25, 2015	An encounter between police commandos and the MILF occurs in a police operation in Mamasapano, Maguindanao, aiming to capture international terrorist Marwan; leading to, in total, 74 deaths including 44 PNP–SAF officers
February 25, 2015	AFP declared its all-out offensive campaign against the MILF breakaway group, the Bangsamoro Islamic Freedom Fighters.
April 14, 2015	Death of Ameril Umbra Kato, the founding leader of the Bangsamoro Islamic Freedom Fighters.
June 28, 2015	Death of Kumander Parago, the top commander of the New People's Army.
June 30, 2015	Globe incorporated Global Capital Venture Holdings, Inc., a wholly owned subsidiary organized under the laws of the Philippines and formed for the purpose of venturing into strategic non-core business.
July 16, 2015	First pairing of the hit television couple, AlDub, on the show Eat Bulaga.
August 27, 2015	Globe Telecom, Inc. (Globe), Ayala Corporation (AC), and Bank of the Philippine Islands (BPI) signed an agreement to turn over full ownership of BPI Globe BanKO (BanKO) to BPI.
September 28, 2015	The Philippine action drama Ang Probinsyano is aired on ABS-CBN.
December 1, 2015	LCpl. Joseph Scott Pemberton is convicted by the court for the death of Jennifer Laude in 2014.
December 21, 2015	Pia Alonzo Wurtzbach is crowned Miss Universe 2015 in Las Vegas, Nevada; the country's first title after 42 years.
December 23, 2015	NTC granted Sky an 18-month provisional license to begin offering direct-to-home satellite, with an initial investment of 252 million pesos to roll-out direct broadcast satellite service across 251 cities and municipalities in the Philippines.
2016	Globe Telecom dislodged Smart Communications as the largest telecommunications company in terms of subscriber base with 65.8 million subscribers. ABS-CBN mobile has a subscriber base of 904,000 bringing its losses to 600 million pesos down from 700 million pesos a year ago.
February 10, 2016	The National Mapping and Resource Information Authority announces that it has documented more than 400 additional islands.
March 23, 2016	Diwata-1 was launched to the International Space Station aboard the Cygnus spacecraft on a supply mission.

April 1, 2016	Philippine Long Distance Telephone Company, dropped the "long distance telephone" from its corporate name and was renamed PLDT Inc.
April 13, 2016	Smart introduced the first commercial LTE-A Service in Boracay, Aklan.
May 9, 2016	The 2016 Philippine presidential election results in Davao City mayor Rodrigo Duterte is elected as the first President from Mindanao
May 23, 2016	Former President Aquino III signed Republic Act No. 10844 creating the Department of Information and Communications Technology (DICT) and making the NTC an attached agency of the newly created executive department.
June 13, 2016	PLDT and its subsidiary Smart unveiled their new logos and identity as part of the company's continuing digital pivot.
July 1, 2016	An intensified nationwide anti-drug campaign is launched by President Rodrigo Duterte.
July 12, 2016	The Permanent Court of Arbitration rules in favor of the Philippines against China over territorial disputes in the South China Sea.
July 19, 2016	The Supreme Court acquits former President Gloria Macapagal Arroyo of her plunder case regarding the alleged misuse of funds for the PCSO in an 11-4 ruling.
July 23, 2016	Former President Rodrigo Duterte signs an executive order for the implementation of the Freedom of Information (FOI).
August 1, 2016	Launch of the 911 emergency number and 8888 civil service complaint hotline.
November 1, 2016	Sun has been integrated into the Smart network in terms of mobile network infrastructure and corporate management.
November 18, 2016	The controversial burial of Ferdinand Marcos at the Libingan ng mga Bayani.
December 1, 2016	ABS-CBN mobile launched their own 4G LTE service.
July 9, 1905	GCash, and PayMaya, partnered with Facebook to integrate its services with Facebook Messenger.
January 1, 2017	Sky Cable Corporation had 1.4 million customers across the country, 200,000 of which are broadband internet subscribers.
January 11, 2017	Former President Rodrigo Duterte signed an executive order mandating universal access to modern family planning tools.
February 1, 2017	Smart and parent company PLDT signed a memorandum of understanding with China-based Huawei Technologies "to shape the strategic and commercial development of the 5G ecosystem in the Philippines".
February 5, 2017	Former President Rodrigo Duterte designates the Communist Party of the Philippines-New Peoples Army (CPP-NPA) as a terrorist organization following attacks and kidnappings of soldiers by NPA members amid the imposed ceasefire between the government and the communist rebels.
February 24, 2017	Arrest of Leila de Lima for violations of Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002, related to her alleged involvement in the New Bilibid Prison drug trafficking scandal.
February 28, 2017	Philippines' signing of the Paris Agreement on Climate Change.

April 21, 2017	Former President Duterte signed Republic Act No. 10926 which renewed Smart's license for another 25 years.
May 16, 2017	Former President Rodrigo Duterte signed Executive Order No. 25, that renamed Benham Rise to Philippine Rise, as well as Executive Order No. 26, that ordered a nationwide smoking ban.
May 23, 2017	Former President Rodrigo Duterte declares a 60-day martial law in Mindanao following clashes between government forces and the Maute group in Marawi City.
July 22, 2017	Congress votes to extend martial law in Mindanao until the end of 2017 as siege in Marawi City continues.
October 16, 2017	Abu Sayyaf leader Isnilon Hapilon and Maute group leader Omar Maute are killed by government troops in an assault.
October 17, 2017	Former President Rodrigo Duterte declares the liberation of Marawi City.
November 27, 2017	Globe Telecom's CEO, Ernest Cu was named the CEO of the year by the World Communication Awards 2017.
July 16, 2018	ABS-CBN and Globe Telecom announced that it will not renew their network-sharing agreement after assessing its mobile business model as financially unsustainable, making ABS-CBN mobile shut down during the year.
July 26, 2018	The Bangsamoro Organic Law is signed into law by President Rodrigo Duterte, providing for the basic structure of government for the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao.
October 1, 2018	petitioners asked the Supreme Court to stop Globe and Smart from using the 700 MHz and Smart announced that they were working to fix its slow internet service.
October 16, 2018	ABS-CBN mobile posts an announcement regarding its shutdown.
November 7, 2018	Mislattel was one of the telecommunication firms to join the government-sanctioned bidding allowing the winner to become the third major telco provider in the Philippines challenging the duopoly of PLDT and Globe. Mislattel became a joint-consortium between Udenna Corporation, its subsidiary Chelsea Logistics, and parent company of China Telecom.
November 30, 2018	ABS-CBN mobile announces its shutdown.
December 1, 2018	ABS-CBN mobile was officially discontinued of all services and the network signal from Globe will be permanently deactivated until further notice.
October 17, 2018	Globe Telecom was selected as the best workplace in Asia.
October 29, 2018	Converge ICT's coverage and service has matured enough to be a viable contender for the spot to becoming the 3rd major telecommunications company in the Philippines.
February 6, 2019	The Senate and the House of Representatives approved the transfer of ownership of Mislattel to the China telecom consortium.
February 17, 2019	Smart and its parent company PLDT launched Omega Esports, a professional esports team for DOTA 2, Mobile Legends: Bang Bang, and Tekken 7.

August 18, 2019	Eastern provided a digital kiosk named MNLKonek (initially known as Iskonek) in partnership with the City Government of Manila which offers free Wi-Fi connection, calls, and phone charging.
June 14, 2019	China Telecom stakeholders completed a share-purchase agreement with Mislattel, and were then awaiting their permit to operate.
July 8, 2019	Mislattel was renamed as Dito Telecommunity. Dito Telecommunity was granted its permit to operate after former President Duterte awarded the Certificate of Public Convenience and Necessity by the NTC.
September 6, 2019	Dito announced its plans to build its own campus on an 8-hectare (20-acre) lot at Clark Global City.
October 1, 2019	Dito Telecommunity signed an agreement with Sky. Under the deal, Dito will utilize Sky's unused fiber-optic cables in Metro Manila.
October 4, 2019	Dito signed separate deals with Lopez-owned Sky Cable Corporation and politician Luis Chavit Singson's LCS Group. Under the deal with LCS Group, Dito will lease the shared telco towers that LCS had already build in several areas.
February 2020	GCash partnered with Philippine Seven Corporation to pay in 7-Eleven branches via barcode throughout the country. GCash also partnered with Ministop to expand cash-in services. Smart is noted to have 73 million mobile subscribers under the brands Smart, Sun, and TNT. Smart's wireless broadband subscribers number 3.8 million under the brands Smart Bro and Sun Wireless Broadband.
February 1, 2020	Sun's logo has been changed to reflect it being a full-blown brand of Smart.
March 1, 2020	The first domestic and international calls from the Dito company's network were made.
March 12, 2020	Former President Duterte announced a partial lockdown covering the entirety of Metro Manila that was later put into place on March 15.
March 15, 2020	A partial lockdown is implemented, covering the entirety of Metro Manila
March 16, 2020	Luzon placed under Enhanced Community Quarantine in response to the growing pandemic of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) in the country.
March 20, 2020	Senator Koko Pimentel III took the test for COVID-19.
March 23, 2020	Former President Duterte signed Administrative Order No. 26, granting that front line government officials and employees receive a daily hazard pay of ₱500.
March 24, 2020	Former President Duterte signed Bayanihan 1 Act. Former Vice President Leni Robredo's office had delivered 23,475 sets of PPE to 62 medical facilities and communities across Metro Manila, La Union, and Quezon.
March 25, 2020	Senator Koko Pimentel III was tested positive for COVID-19, while his wife is also giving birth at the Makati Medical Center.

March 31, 2020	The Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE) reported that at least 25,428 formal sectors and 5,220 informal sector workers were given cash assistance of ₱5,000 each.
April 1, 2020	<p>Around 150 protesters called on the local government for food aid amid the enhance community quarantine in Luzon.</p> <p>Former President Duterte made a controversial speech where he stated that quarantine violators will be shot.</p> <p>NBI sent an invitation letter to Pasig City Mayor Vico Sotto for violation of Bayanihan to Heal as One Act.</p>
April 2, 2020	The hashtag #OustDuterte and #OustDuterteNow trended again on social media which garnered 327,000 tweets following Duterte's remarks of ordering to "shoot" the violators of COVID-19 quarantine protocol during his speech on April 1.
April 7, 2020	NBI Deputy Director Ferdinand Lavin said that Sotto was scheduled to appear at the bureau.
April 11, 2020	GMA News anchor Arnold Clavio alleged through his social media account that one hospital in Metro Manila was told not count COVID-19 deaths.
April 14, 2020	Around ₱57.8 billion have been released by the social welfare department to the country's 103 local government units.
April 21, 2020	Former Corporal Winston Ragos was shot dead by police for allegedly attempting to pull a gun at a checkpoint while the country was under enhanced community quarantine. Witnesses say Ragos did not have a gun and his mother claimed her son was suffering from post-traumatic stress disorder.
April 26, 2020	Former Corporal Ragos is buried at the Libingan ng mga Bayani.
April 27, 2020	Police Senior Master Sergeant Roland Von Madrona and Bantay Bayan personnel Esteban Gaan were patrolling the village and saw Javier Parra and his housemaid, Cherilyn Escalante, watering plants outside his property's perimeter without wearing a face mask. Parra prompts to humiliate and hurl at the police.
April 30, 2020	Madrona files a criminal case against Parra.
May 8, 2020	National Capital Region Police Office (NCRPO) personnel celebrated the birthday of their chief Maj. Gen. Debold Sinas at Camp Bagong Diwa.
May 13, 2020	The pictures of Sinas birthday party were circulated on the internet.

May 17, 2020	The DSWD had reached 95 percent of its target, providing aid to 17.1 million beneficiary households with ₱96.7 billion worth of cash subsidy distributed.
May 15, 2020	PNP filed criminal charges against Sinas and 18 other officers who attended his birthday for violating quarantine guidelines.
June 30, 2020	NTC issued a cease and desist order against Sky's direct-broadcast satellite service, Sky Direct.
July 3, 2020	The Anti-Terrorism Act of 2020 is signed into law by President Rodrigo Duterte, giving more surveillance powers to government forces to curb terror threats and acts.
July 18, 2020	Dito Telecommunity had its technical launch.
July 20, 2020	The 2020 State of the Nation Address was the fifth State of the Nation Address delivered by former President Rodrigo Duterte. He ordered Smart Communications and Globe Telecom to improve their services in the next five months and warned local government units to act on permit applications of telecommunications firms within three days or be charged with corruption or face possible suspension.
July 30, 2020	Smart activated their 5G mobile network initially in Makati Central Business District, Bonifacio Global City CBD, Araneta City, SM Megamall and Mall of Asia Bay Area.
September 2020	Members of the Presidential Security Group, or PSG were vaccinated, according to Brig. Gen. Jesus Durante III.
September 1, 2020	Dito has completed 859 cell sites out of the planned 1,600 sites that will cover 37% of the population.
September 11, 2020	Former President Duterte signed Bayanihan 2 Act.
October 1, 2020	Converge ICT Solutions Inc. is reported to debut in the Philippine Stock Exchange. Globe Telecom launched "GOMO", the country's first fully digital telco.
October 21, 2020	PLDT announced that Sun's prepaid service was integrated into Smart Prepaid, leaving its postpaid service under "Sun" branding.
December 2020	Former President Duterte stated that some members of the military received COVID-19 vaccine from Sinopharm despite the vaccine not yet officially approved.
December 28, 2020	The Armed Forces of the Philippines said that the PSG members were the first ones to be vaccinated to "protect" Duterte.
December 29, 2020	FDA Director General Enrique Domingo said that the DOH and the FDA were not consulted over the inoculation of soldiers and other government officials.
December 30, 2020	Durante said that he will take "full responsibility" for the vaccine administered to the PSG.

January 4, 2021	Former President Duterte ordered the PSG to either not attend any congressional meeting regarding the unauthorized vaccination or stay quiet during such a hearing, contradicting the Presidential Spokesperson who said that the PSG will submit to any investigation.
January 5, 2021	Despite former President Duterte's threat of a potential "crisis" if senators questioned his military bodyguards, the Senate opened an investigation for the unauthorized use of COVID-19 vaccines.
January 6, 2021	Senator Sherwin Gatchalian said he found nothing wrong with giving vaccines to PSG members since they were considered frontliners, though he acknowledged and took issue with the fact that the vaccines were brought into the country illegally.
February 1, 2021	Eastern announced a nationwide upgrade program with the company spending a budget of ₱2.8 billion to expand its services in Davao City, Cagayan de Oro, Dumaguete, Tagbilaran, Bacolod, Roxas, Kalibo, Caticlan, Boracay, Naga, Legazpi, Iriga and Sorsogon province. Dito Telecommunity passed its first technical audit.
February 23, 2021	Dito and PLDT signed an interconnection deal to enable subscribers from the two companies to communicate in their respective networks.
February 24, 2021	Dito and Globe Telecom signed an interconnection deal to enable subscribers from the two companies to communicate in their respective networks.
March 8, 2021	Dito Telecommunity began its commercial operations.
March 15, 2021	After a year of the declaration of the community quarantine in Metro Manila, #DutertePalpak went trending on social media. Netizens blamed the government for the resurgence of cases and its lack of proper response to the pandemic.
March 16, 2021	People's Television Network, accidentally placed the hashtag on their social media post regarding the provision of masks.
March 22, 2021	Converge ICT says that a deal "is on" with Satellite Internet provider Starlink.
March 24, 2021	Former President Duterte named in his public address nine different mayors who jumped the vaccination priority line.
March 29, 2021	Former President Duterte gave his last address about the pandemic.
April 13, 2021	Dito began the construction of its Clark Global City campus.
April 7, 2021	Duterte's cancellation of his weekly national address triggered the hashtag #NasaanAngPangulo.

April 8, 2021	Senator Bong Go posted a picture of Duterte seated at a table with various documents.
April 10, 2021	Senator Bong Go posted another picture of Duterte riding a motorcycle and jogging at night.
April 14, 2021	A community pantry was first established on Maginhawa Street in Quezon City by 26-year-old organizer Ana Patricia Non.
April 16, 2021	Dito expanded its services to select areas in Luzon provinces, initially in five provinces covering a total of 18 cities and municipalities.
April 23, 2021	Facebook posts made by Quezon City Police Department and NTF-ELCAC that claimed the pantries "are being used by communist groups for their propaganda.
May 17, 2021	Dito service became available in Metro Manila.
May 18, 2021	Former President Duterte signed Republic Act No. 11537 which renewed Dito's license for another 25 years.
May 26, 2021	Dito selected Nokia to deploy its 5G services in Mindanao.
June 22, 2021	Former President Duterte threatens Filipinos that they will be arrested if they refuse vaccination.
June 23, 2021	The Anti-Terrorism Council designates the National Democratic Front (NDF) as a terrorist organization, citing it as an "integral and inseparable part" of the CPP-NPA.
June 29, 2021	Dito announced that it has partnered with non-banking financial firm M Lhuillier to expand the reach of the former's products and services nationwide.
July 25, 2021	GCash announced that its remittance service, GCash Padala, is now available to non-app users through its 2,000 partners nationwide.
September 10, 2021	A video of Presidential spokesperson Harry Roque berating the doctors who opposed the implementation of general community quarantine (GCQ) during the IATF meeting was released to the public.
September 24, 2021	Pharmally's Krizle Mago admitted that the firm tampered with the expiration dates of face shields and that the firm delivered "substandard" face shields to the Department of Health (DOH).
September 26, 2021	Pharmally's Krizle Mago cannot be contacted anymore.
November 1, 2021	GCash's parent company, Mynt, announced that it raised \$300M in funding at a \$2B valuation.
December 20, 2021	Gwyneth Anne Chua skipped the mandatory quarantine upon arrival in the Philippines from Los Angeles.
December 23, 2021	Chua was fetched by her father to attend a party held in Barangay Poblacion in Makati.

December 25, 2021	Chua was transported back to Berjaya Hotel.
December 26, 2021	Chua underwent swab test and the result came out positive for COVID-19 the next day.
January 3, 2022	The Criminal Investigation and Detection Group (CIDG) planned to file charges against Chua, along with eight other people, for violating the sections of Republic Act No. 11332
January 5, 2022	DOT suspended the accreditation of Berjaya Makati Hotel for three months over breaching the quarantine policy, giving them 15 working days to appeal the decision.
January 11, 2022	The GCash mobile application and its services were briefly interrupted due to a power outage that lasted for four hours.
January 17, 2022	Department Order No. 2022-001 or the "no vaccination, no ride" policy in Metro Manila takes effect, as the country continues to log record-high numbers due to the Omicron-fueled surge.
February 1, 2022	The average fixed broadband download speeds rose from 7.91 Mbit/s to 82.61 Mbit/s, a 944% growth. Average mobile internet speeds have also seen a 467% growth at 42.22 Mbit/s from 7.44 Mbit/s since the start of the Duterte administration.
February 24, 2022	Statista reports that the Internet penetration rate in the Philippines is accounted to be at 72.7%, and the number of internet users in the Philippines equate to 79.66 million.
February 28, 2022	Dito launches its pilot broadband in Metro Manila instead.
March 27, 2022	Satellite internet service provider Starlink has received approval of its registration from the National Telecommunications Commission
April 25, 2022	Sun's postpaid service was merged with Smart Postpaid, resulting to the subsequent forced retirement of all Sun Postpaid plans and add-ons. Smart encouraged those planning to subscribe to Sun to instead take advantage of Smart Signature plans, while existing subscribers can either still use their current subscription plans or upgrade to Smart Signature.
May 9, 2022	The 2022 Philippine general election are held, marking the first majority win since the establishment of the Fifth Republic in 1987, the first presidential ticket to win together since 2004, and the return of the Marcos family to power since the People Power Revolution. (Bongbong Marcos is elected as President alongside his running mate, Sara Duterte, as Vice President)
July 1, 2022	Dito service is currently available in 53 out of 81 provinces in the country: 29 in Luzon, nine in Visayas and 15 in Mindanao.
August 1, 2022	GCash Jr. was launched. Dito's total mobile subscriber base reached 12 million.
August 8, 2022	Dito Telecommunity filed a complaint against duopolies Globe Telecom and Smart Communications at the Philippine Competition Commission for an alleged "anti-competitive practice" and "abuse of market dominance".

August 9, 2022	Globe Telecom has asked NTC to pay the interconnection penalty of ₱622 million to Dito Telecommunity for "breach of agreement".
August 10, 2022	Cignal Cable Corporation, a subsidiary of MediaQuest Holdings, will acquire a 38.88% minority stake of Sky Cable Corporation through the execution of a "debt instruments agreement", with an option to acquire an additional 61.12% of Sky Cable shares within the next eight years.
August 24, 2022	ABS-CBN and TV5 agreed to pause their closing preparations for the deal following concerns from politicians and some government agencies.
September 1, 2022	ABS-CBN and TV5 announced the termination of the proposed investment.
October 10, 2022	President Ferdinand Marcos Jr. signs the SIM Card Registration Act.

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Investigating who is Mrs. Redgrave and a possible lead to who she is.
(Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Investigating the Banahaw Broadcasting Corporation via the Canciones de Filipinas (CDF) Discord server. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

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Appendices: Google Forms Survey and Survey Answers

The image displays two screenshots of a Google Forms survey interface. The top screenshot shows the 'Questions' tab, featuring a header image of a church tower, the title 'Communication of Younger QCitizens: A Short Survey to Senior High School students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School', and an introductory paragraph. Below the text is a 'Name' question with a 'Short answer' dropdown menu. The bottom screenshot shows the 'Responses' tab, which displays '0 responses' and a red banner indicating 'Not accepting responses'. A message for respondents states, 'This form is no longer accepting responses.'

Editing the survey form in Google Forms. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Survey Form: Communication of Younger QCitizens (Responses) ☆ ☰ ☾

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Name	Email Address	By clicking or tapping "I agree"	Gender	Grade Level and Strand	What devices do you use	How do you use your devices	On average, how many hours	Which social media plat	With the p
2		Yes, I agree to participate	Female	Grade 12 - ABM	Laptop, Tablet, Smartphone	Home WiFi, Mobile Data	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes
3		Yes, I agree to participate	Male	Grade 12 - ABM	Laptop, Smartphone	Home WiFi, Mobile Data	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes
4		Yes, I agree to participate	Female	Grade 12 - ABM	Laptop, Smartphone	Home WiFi, Mobile Data	4-6 hours	Facebook, TikTok, YouTube	No
5		Yes, I agree to participate	Male	Grade 12 - ABM	Desktop Computer	Home WiFi	1-3 hours	Facebook, Gmail, YouTube	No
6		Yes, I agree to participate	Female	Grade 12 - ABM	Tablet	Mobile Data	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Instagram, TikTok	Yes
7		Yes, I agree to participate	Male	Grade 12 - ABM	Smartphone	Home WiFi	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes
8		Yes, I agree to participate	Part of the LGBTQI+	Grade 12 - ABM	Tablet, Smartphone	Home WiFi, Mobile Data	More than 6 hours	Facebook, YouTube	Yes
9		Yes, I agree to participate	Female	Grade 12 - ABM	Laptop, Tablet	Mobile Data	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Gmail, YouTube	Yes
10		Yes, I agree to participate	Female	Grade 12 - ABM	Laptop, Tablet	Home WiFi	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Instagram, TikTok	Maybe
11		Yes, I agree to participate	Male	Grade 12 - STEM	Smartphone	Home WiFi, Mobile Data	1-3 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Discord	Yes
12		Yes, I agree to participate	Male	Grade 12 - STEM	Laptop, Tablet	Home WiFi	1-3 hours	Facebook, YouTube	No
13		Yes, I agree to participate	Male	Grade 12 - STEM	Smartphone	Home WiFi, Mobile Data	Less than an hour	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes
14		Yes, I agree to participate	Female	Grade 12 - ABM	Tablet	Mobile Data	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes
15		Yes, I agree to participate	Male	Grade 11 - STEM	Laptop, Smartphone	Home WiFi, Internet Caffe	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	No
16		Yes, I agree to participate	Part of the LGBTQI+	Grade 12 - STEM	Desktop Computer, Laptop	Home WiFi, Internet Caffe	4-6 hours	Facebook, Instagram, TikTok	Yes
17		Yes, I agree to participate	Male	Grade 11 - HEMSS	Laptop, Smartphone	Home WiFi, Mobile Data	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Instagram, TikTok	No
18		Yes, I agree to participate	Female	Grade 11 - STEM	Desktop Computer, Laptop	Home WiFi, Internet Caffe	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes
19		Yes, I agree to participate	Part of the LGBTQI+	Grade 12 - HEMSS	Laptop, Smartphone	Home WiFi, Mobile Data	1-3 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes
20		Yes, I agree to participate	Male	Grade 12 - STEM	Laptop, Smartphone	Home WiFi	1-3 hours	Facebook, YouTube	Yes
21		Yes, I agree to participate	Prefer not to say	Grade 11 - STEM	Desktop Computer, Laptop	Home WiFi, Internet Caffe	4-6 hours	Facebook, Instagram, TikTok	No
22		Yes, I agree to participate	Prefer not to say	Grade 11 - GAS	Smartphone	Home WiFi, Internet Caffe	4-6 hours	Facebook, Instagram, Siri	No
23		Yes, I agree to participate	Female	Grade 12 - ABM	Desktop Computer, Smart	Home WiFi	1-3 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes
24		Yes, I agree to participate	Part of the LGBTQI+	Grade 12 - GAS	Desktop Computer, Tablet	Home WiFi, Internet Caffe	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes
25		Yes, I agree to participate	Female	Grade 11 - GAS	Desktop Computer, Laptop	Home WiFi, Internet Caffe	4-6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes
26		Yes, I agree to participate	Female	Grade 11 - HEMSS	Laptop, Smartphone	Home WiFi, Internet Caffe	4-6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes
27		Yes, I agree to participate	Part of the LGBTQI+	Grade 11 - HEMSS	Laptop, Smartphone	Apartment / Dormitory W	4-6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, TikTok	Yes
28		Yes, I agree to participate	Male	Grade 11 - ABM	Laptop, Smartphone	Home WiFi, Mobile Data	4-6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes
29		Yes, I agree to participate	Female	Grade 12 - GAS	Desktop Computer, Laptop	Home WiFi, Internet Caffe	1-3 hours	Facebook, Gmail, Yahoo	Yes
30		Yes, I agree to participate	Female	Grade 11 - STEM	Desktop Computer, Laptop	Home WiFi, Internet Caffe	4-6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	No
31		Yes, I agree to participate	Male	Grade 11 - HEMSS	Laptop, Tablet	Neighbor's WiFi, Internet	4-6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes

Form Responses 1

Survey Form: Communication of Younger QCitizens (Responses) ☆ ☰ ☾

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On average, how many hours	Which social media plat	With the presence of the	social media presence	As you have returned be	Would you say that being	Do you believe that being	Do you agree pandemic	As a student of a public	Do you be
7	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Maybe	Maybe
8	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
9	4-6 hours	Facebook, TikTok, YouTube	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Maybe	Maybe	Maybe
10	1-3 hours	Facebook, Gmail, YouTube	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
11	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
12	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
13	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Gmail, YouTube	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
14	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Instagram, TikTok	Maybe	Maybe	Maybe	Maybe	Maybe	Maybe	Maybe
15	1-3 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Discord	No	Yes	Maybe	Maybe	Maybe	Maybe	Yes
16	1-3 hours	Facebook, YouTube	Yes	Yes	Maybe	No	Yes	Maybe	Maybe
17	Less than an hour	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Maybe	Maybe
18	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes	Yes	Maybe	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
19	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Maybe	Maybe
20	4-6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Maybe	Yes
21	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Instagram, TikTok	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
22	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
23	1-3 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	No	No	No	Yes	Maybe	Maybe	Maybe
24	1-3 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
25	More than 6 hours	Facebook, Instagram, TikTok	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
26	4-6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
27	4-6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	No	No	Maybe	Maybe	Maybe	Maybe	Maybe
28	4-6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
29	4-6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
30	1-3 hours	Facebook, Gmail, Yahoo	Yes	No	Maybe	Maybe	No	Yes	No
31	4-6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	No	Maybe	Maybe	Yes	Yes	Maybe	Yes
32	4-6 hours	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes

Form Responses 1

Answers of the survey form in Google Sheets. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Gender Distribution

Gender distribution of the respondents. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Grade Level and Strand

Grade level and strand of the respondents. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Used Devices by Students

Combined devices used by students. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Used Devices by Students

Devices used by students. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Student Device Connectivity

Combined methods of connectivity of devices that are used by students.
(Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Student Device Connectivity

Summarized methods of connectivity of devices that are used by students.
(Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Hours of Device Use

Number of hours that students use their devices. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Social Media Platforms of Students

The different social media platforms that students use. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

With the presence of many social media platforms, do you still use your short messaging service (SMS) application in smartphones for personal communication?

Answers in Survey Question #1. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Is social media presence a consideration when doing your personal activities?

Answers in Survey Question #2. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

As you have returned back to your face-to-face classes, is social media presence still a major consideration when doing your academic activities?

Answers in Survey Question #3. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Would you say that being active social media influences your goals in life?

Answers in Survey Question #4. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Do you believe that being the "City of Stars", Quezon City must be a role model for improving the communication for every Filipino?

Answers in Survey Question #5. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Do you agree pandemic affected the effectivity and / or range of communication and mass media within the city during the past two years?

Answers in Survey Question #6. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

As a student of a public high school within the city, do you believe that Quezon City is doing well in disseminating information to its constituents?

Answers in Survey Question #7. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Do you believe that being immersed in social media made contacting the city's different departments easier to the residents?

Answers in Survey Question #8 (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Communication of Younger QCitizens: A Short Survey to Senior High School students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School

Hi there! If you are a bona fide Senior High School student of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School, I would really appreciate it if you could please take a couple of minutes to fill out the survey below as part of my requirement in one of my subjects. This survey contains an information letter and consent form at the beginning, allowing the participant to read what the study entails. If consent is given, click the 'Yes' option on the form prior to proceeding with the questionnaire. Thank you very much, and have a great day!

* Required

1. Name: *

2. Email Address: *

Questionnaire Information Sheet:

Project Title: *Communication Over the City of Stars: Inspecting Quezon City's Evolution as a Discourse Hub*

Dear participant,

I, Marc Andrie Bermundo, am pursuing my Bachelor of Science in Physics degree at the University of the Philippines, Baguio. I would like to invite you to take part in my survey paper in the subject, Critical Perspectives in Communication. Please take time to read the following information carefully, and feel free to ask questions if anything you read is not clear to you or if you'd like more information.

What is my survey paper about?

My survey paper is about the development of Quezon City as a place of communication, specifically with how it became integral to the formation of the most influential media-based companies in the Philippines. In this specific part of said survey paper, I decided that I'll check out on the case of Senior High School students of my former school, Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School.

What will you be asked to do in this study?

I hope that you will be willing to participate in a questionnaire that will take approximately **5-10** minutes to complete. I would like to gain insights into your experiences of communication, especially within your loved ones and peers.

Are there any risks involved in participating in this study?

This is a low-risk study that is done remotely, all concerns regarding COVID-19 protocols can be set aside. Only your email will be required but not shared.

What are the benefits of being involved in this study?

While you may not benefit directly from this study, findings from this survey paper may be helpful for you to inquire yourselves about how you use different mediums of communication on a daily basis.

Will my details be kept confidential?

Only your name and email address will be necessary in my submission of the survey paper. This information will not be shared.

Who do I contact for further information?

Should you require any further information, please do not hesitate to contact me, Marc Andrie Bermundo, on my email, marcandrie.bermundo@gmail.com.

In accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, please note further information regarding data management and storage:

1. The right to access my personal information.

2. The right to make corrections to my personal information.
3. The right to object to the processing of my personal information.
4. The right to erasure or blocking of my personal information.
5. The right to be informed of the existence of processing my personal information.
6. The right to damages.
7. The right to lodge a complaint before the National Privacy Commission.

The data will be kept in spreadsheet format under the secured storage of Google Forms, Google Sheets, and the local computer drives of those involved.

This information sheet is for you to be aware of the purpose of the study. By agreeing to consent on the next form, you indicate that you understand the purpose of the survey.

Informed Consent:

Researcher: Marc Andrie Bermundo

Please read the following to show your agreement and understanding of what is expected for this study.

1. You are a bona fide student of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School, under the Senior High School Department.
2. You confirm that you have read and understood the information sheet explaining the above survey paper and have had the opportunity to ask questions about it.
3. You understand that your participation is voluntary and that you are free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason and without there being any negative consequences.
4. You understand that no personal data will be collected from you.
5. You give permission for the researcher to have access to my responses without revealing any part of my identity.
6. You understand that your name will not be linked with the research materials, and that you will not be identified or identifiable in the survey paper.
7. You agree for the **anonymized** data collected in this survey.

3. By clicking or tapping "I agree", you are accepting to answer all of the questions that are present in this survey. *

Mark only one oval.

Yes, I agree to participate.

4. Gender *

Mark only one oval.

Male

Female

Part of the LGBTQI+

Prefer not to say

5. Grade Level and Strand *

Mark only one oval.

Grade 11 - STEM

Grade 11 - ABM

Grade 11 - HUMSS

Grade 11 - GAS

Grade 12 - STEM

Grade 12 - ABM

Grade 12 - HUMSS

Grade 12 - GAS

6. What devices do you personally use for communication? (Check all that apply) *

Check all that apply.

- Desktop Computer
- Laptop
- Tablet
- Smartphone

7. How do your devices connect to the Internet? (Check all that apply) *

Check all that apply.

- Home WiFi
- Neighbor's WiFi
- Apartment / Dormitory WiFi
- Internet Cafes
- Nearby Establishments / Public Places
- Mobile Data

8. On average, how many hours a day do you use social media? *

Mark only one oval.

- Less than an hour
- 1-3 hours
- 4-6 hours
- More than 6 hours

9. Which social media platforms do you use on a personal basis? (Check all that apply) *

Check all that apply.

- Facebook
- Twitter
- Instagram
- TikTok
- Discord
- Snapchat
- WhatsApp
- Viber
- Tumblr
- Pinterest
- Telegram
- Tinder
- Bumble
- Omegle
- Ask.FM
- CuriousCat
- Gmail
- Yahoo
- VKontakte
- YouTube
- Other: _____

10. With the presence of many social media platforms, do you still use your short messaging service (SMS) application in smartphones for personal communication? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

11. Is social media presence a consideration when doing your personal activities? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Maybe

12. As you have returned back to your face-to-face classes, is social media presence still a major consideration when doing your academic activities? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Maybe

13. Would you say that being active social media influences your goals in life? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Maybe

14. Do you believe that being the "City of Stars", Quezon City must be a role model for improving the communication for every Filipino? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Maybe

15. Do you agree pandemic affected the effectivity and / or range of communication and mass media within the city during the past two years? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Maybe

16. As a student of a public high school within the city, do you believe that Quezon City is doing well in disseminating information to its constituents? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Maybe

17. Do you believe that being immersed in social media made contacting the city's different departments easier to the residents? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Maybe

18. By clicking or tapping "I agree", the answers that you have given to these questions that are present in this survey are truthful and shall be only be processed in a legal manner. *

Mark only one oval.

- I agree.

Survey Completed:

I would like to thank you for giving the time for answering my survey, dear respondent!

Proverbs 16:9 (English Standard Version):

The heart of man plans his way, but the Lord establishes his steps.

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